

AMBIENT-6G

Towards standardized 6G connectivity for ambient-powered energy neutral IoT devices

Deliverable D2.2

Initial Report on END Hardware Design

Co-funded by
the European Union

AMBIENT-6G project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101192113.

Date of delivery: 31th Oct, 2025

Version: 1.0

Project reference: 101192113

Call: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2024

Start date of the project: 1st Jan, 2025

Duration: 36 months

Document properties

Document Number:	D2.2
Document Title:	Initial Report on END Hardware Design
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Contractual Date of Delivery:	31 st Oct, 2025
Dissemination level:	PU
Status:	Final
Version:	1.0
Filename:	AMBIENT-6G_2.2_v1.0

Revision History

Revision	Date	Issued by	Description
v0.1	1 September 2025	AMBIENT-6G WP2	Internal review start.
v0.2	15 September 2025	AMBIENT-6G WP2	External review start.
v1.0	10 October 2025	AMBIENT-6G WP2	Submission to SteerCo.

Abstract:

Deliverable D2.2 advances the results of D2.1 by translating the capability taxonomy of energy-neutral device (END) into implementable hardware. The report consolidates options for light, thermal, vibration, and radio frequency (RF) energy harvesting (EH), together with architectures for dedicated wireless power transfer (WPT). It details efficient RF front ends and charge pumps, and compares ambient and dedicated power paths. It then examines multisource power management, including combining strategies, cold start, prioritization, energy balance monitoring, and voltage limiting, with attention to low quiescent consumption. The document surveys representative low-power device platforms, backscatter communication (BC), and wake-up radios that align communication effort with available energy. A component-level life cycle assessment (LCA) supports responsible choices of materials and modules. The outcomes provide a traceable map from D2.1 classes to hardware building blocks, and prepare the implementation and validation work of D2.3, which will deliver prototypes, reference designs, and measurement-based energy budgets.

Keywords:

AMBIENT-6G, Energy-Neutral Devices, Ambient-IoT, Technology Selection, Hardware Selection, Initial Design, Life Cycle Assessment.

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the issue of Deliverable D2.2: 'Initial Report on END Hardware Design', within the framework of the project titled "AMBIENT-6G-Towards standardized 6G connectivity for ambient-powered energy-neutral IoT devices" (Project Acronym: AMBIENT-6G; Grant Agreement No: 101192113).

This document advances the results of D2.1 by moving from a capability-centric taxonomy toward implementable hardware for energy-neutral device (END). It consolidates energy harvesting (EH) and wireless power transfer options, multisource power management units with protection and monitoring, and low-power communication paths based on backscatter and wake-up radios. In parallel, it surveys representative device platforms with measurable energy profiles and provides an updated view of environmental impact at component level. The result is a coherent map from capability needs to realizable building blocks that operate under intermittent energy while maintaining service quality and reliability.

The contributions of this deliverable are fourfold. First, it provides a compact survey of light, thermal, vibration, and radio frequency (RF) energy sources together with front ends, rectifiers, and charge-pump circuits, and it clarifies when dedicated wireless power transfer (WPT) should complement ambient sources. Second, it describes multisource power management, including cold start, prioritization of inputs, energy balance monitoring, and voltage limiting, with an emphasis on low quiescent consumption. Third, it reports device platforms, backscatter options, and wake-up radio designs that align communication effort with available energy. Fourth, it updates life-cycle considerations so that design choices can reflect environmental impact of materials and manufacturing. The document serves as technical input to integration and validation activities and prepares the ground for more detailed implementation in the next phase.

It should be emphasized that Deliverable D2.2 is an initial report on END hardware design. Consequently, the level of detail across chapters is non-uniform: certain topics, such as photovoltaic (PV) EH and RF charge pumps, already include experimental results, while others, such as unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-based wireless power transfer and energy-aware protocol switching, are presented in outline form with initial insights and results. This reflects the varying maturity of the work within WP2. Subsequent deliverables (D2.3 and D2.4) will expand the less developed parts with consolidated data, integration results, and validation outcomes. The present document should therefore be read as a first snapshot of progress and directions rather than a final account.

In summary, the contents of this document are organized as follows:

- **Chapter 1** presents the motivation, scope, objectives, and overall structure of the report, and positions the work with respect to the taxonomy of D2.1.
- **Chapter 2** covers EH and WPT, including PV and thermoelectric options, RF rectifiers and charge pumps, comparison of ambient and dedicated RF EH, and multisource power management with protection and monitoring.
- **Chapter 3** surveys low-power device platforms together with backscattering-type devices and wake-up radio front ends and processing, linking platform selection and communication choices to energy budgets.

- **Chapter 4** provides an updated life-cycle assessment at component level for boards, communication subsystems, processing, memory, energy storage, incoming energy interfaces, and casing, with guidance for sustainable design decisions.
- **Chapter 5** concludes the document and outlines implications for the next deliverable.

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Glossary

3D three-dimensional.

5G fifth-generation.

ADC analog-to-digital converter.

A-IoT Ambient Internet of Things.

AC alternating current.

AOA angle-of-arrival.

AP access point.

BC backscatter communication.

BD backscatter device.

BGA ball grid array.

BLE Bluetooth Low Energy.

BoM bill of materials.

BPF bandpass filter.

BS base station.

Cat NB2 Category Narrowband IoT Release 14.

CDTE cadmium telluride.

CIGS copper indium gallium selenide.

CMOS complementary metal oxide semiconductor.

COTS commercial off-the-shelf.

CPU central-processing unit.

CSI channel state information.

CSS chirp spread spectrum.

DAC digital-to-analog converter.

DAS distributed antenna systems.

DC direct current.

DECT Digital Enhanced Cordless Telecommunications.

DMA direct memory access.

DRAM dynamic random-access memory.

DSP digital signal processing.

E2E end-to-end.

EC energy combiner.

EDLC electrostatic double-layer capacitors.

EEPROM electrically erasable programmable read-only memory.

EF environmental footprint.

EH energy harvesting.

EMC electromagnetic compatibility.

EN energy neutral.

END energy-neutral device.

EoL end of life.

ESD electrostatic discharge.

eSIM embedded subscriber identity module.

ET energy transmitter.

ETSI European Telecommunications Standards Institute.

FDMA frequency division multiple access.

FFT fast Fourier transform.

FPGA field-programmable gate array.

FSK frequency shift keying.

GNSS global navigation satellite system.

GPIO general-purpose input/output.

GPS Global Positioning System.

GWP Global Warming Potential.

HASL Hot Air Solder Leveling.

IC integrated circuit.

IO input/output.

IoT Internet of Things.

IPT inductive power transfer.

ISM industrial, scientific and medical.

LCA life cycle assessment.

LCD liquid-crystal display.

LCO lithium cobalt oxide.

LDO low-dropout voltage regulator.

LED light emitting diode.

LiPo lithium polymer.

LMO lithium ion manganese oxide.

LoRa long range.

LPF low-pass filter.

LPM Low Power Management.

LTC lithium thionyl chloride.

LTE Long Term Evolution.

LTE-M Long Term Evolution for Machines.

LTO lithium titanate.

MA movable antenna.

MCU microcontroller unit.

MEC multi-access edge computing.

MIMO multiple-input multiple-output.

MISO multiple-input single-output.

ML machine learning.

mMTC massive machine-typed communication.

MOS metal-oxide semiconductor.

MPPT maximum power point tracking.

MRC magnetic resonance coupling.

NB-IoT narrowband IoT.

NFC near-field communication.

NLoS non-line-of-sight.

NMOS N-channel metal-oxide semiconductor.

NR New Radio.

OCV open circuit voltage.

OFDM orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing.

OOK on-off keying.

PA power amplifier.

PCB printed circuit board.

PCE power conversion efficiency.

PDCCH physical downlink control channel.

PET polyethylene terephthalate.

PET privacy enhancing technology.

PLA polylactic acid.

PLA physically large array.

PLL phase-locked loop.

PMIC power management integrated circuit.

PMOS P-channel metal-oxide semiconductor.

PMU power management unit.

PSM power saving mode.

PTAT proportional to absolute temperature.

PV photovoltaic.

PWM pulse width modulation.

QoS quality-of-service.

RAM random-access memory.

RAT radio access technology.

RF radio frequency.

RF EH radio frequency energy harvesting.

RFID radio frequency identification.

RF WPT radio frequency wireless power transmission.

RIS reflective intelligent surface.

ROM read-only memory.

SIM subscriber identity module.

SiP system-in-package.

SISO single-input single-output.

SLIPT simultaneous light information and power transfer.

SMD surface mount device.

SMPS switched mode power supply.

SNR signal-to-noise ratio.

SoC state of charge.

SRAM static random-access memory.

TDMA time division-multiple access.

TEG thermoelectric generator.

THT through-hole technology.

TPU thermoplastic polyurethane.

UART universal asynchronous receiver/transmitter.

UAV unmanned aerial vehicle.

UHF ultra-high frequency.

URLLC ultra-reliable low-latency communications.

USB universal serial bus.

VCO voltage-controlled oscillator.

VLC visible light communication.

VSWR voltage standing wave ratio.

WEEE waste electrical and electronic equipment.

Wi-Fi wireless fidelity.

WPT wireless power transfer.

Chapter 1

Introduction

In this chapter, the context from D2.1 and link to the current deliverable is first introduced. Then, the motivation of this deliverable is illustrated, following by the scope and objectives. Finally, the structure of the document is presented.

1.1 Context from D2.1 and Link to the Present Deliverable

Deliverable D2.1 sets a common language for energy-neutral device (END) by introducing a capability-centric taxonomy and an alpha–numeric coding that captures energy storage, incoming energy, interfaces, processing, communication, and memory. The document also grouped devices into four operation-oriented classes, namely ultra-passive, duty-cycled barebone, duty-cycled persistent, and continuous operation, and connected these classes with typical applications and environmental considerations. The result was a coherent framework that characterizes devices according to architectural components and operational limits, which facilitates comparison across prototypes and use cases.

D2.1 further argued that sustainable connectivity requires devices that operate autonomously with minimal maintenance through harvesting of ambient energy or wireless power transfer. This perspective underpins the vision of long-lived, low-impact operation in massive Internet of Things (IoT) deployments. The classification was not an end in itself. It was intended to guide the selection of device classes for specific use cases and to align device capabilities with constraints in protocol and network design.

The present deliverable, D2.2, picks up from that foundation and focuses on hardware solutions that enable autonomous operation of low-power IoT devices. It moves from classification and trade-off analysis to concrete building blocks and integration practices, covering energy harvesting (EH) and power transfer circuits, multisource power management, low-power device platforms including backscatter options and wake-up radios, and a refined life-cycle assessment of typical components. These topics map the pathway from a device capability code to an implementable hardware stack that sustains operation under intermittent energy. For these purposes, D2.2 provides input to subsequent design, integration, and validation tasks, while maintaining traceability to the device classes and sustainability objectives that D2.1 established.

The present deliverable constitutes the initial report on END hardware design, consistent with the Description of Action. The non-uniformity of the presentation reflects the natural progression

of research and development across different hardware components: some building blocks are already mature and can be reported with measured results, while others are at a conceptual or early implementation stage and serve to outline the upcoming work. This staged approach ensures traceability of progress and prepares the ground for the more comprehensive reports in D2.3 and D2.4.

1.2 Motivation

Massive IoT adoption depends on reliable operation of devices that rely on minimal or no battery maintenance. Replacing or recharging batteries at scale inflates cost, reduces service availability, and increases environmental footprint. The AMBIENT-6G vision emphasizes energy neutrality through the harvesting of light, heat, vibration, and radio frequency energy, as well as controlled wireless power transfer. This vision leads to autonomous operation that fits stringent constraints of cost, form factor, and sustainability.

Practical realization requires hardware that is efficient at low power, resilient to variability of ambient sources, and capable of safe energy handling. Devices must convert weak and fluctuating sources into stored energy, schedule tasks according to energy availability, and communicate with minimal overhead. The motivation for this deliverable is to bridge architectural intent and field-ready hardware. It addresses energy harvesters such as photovoltaic (PV) cells and thermoelectric generators (TEGs), charge-pump front ends for radio frequency energy harvesting (RF EH), and transmitter for wireless power transfer (WPT) including ground infrastructure and mobile platforms such as unmanned aerial vehicles. It also considers multisource power management, energy combiners, and techniques for energy balance monitoring and voltage limiting.

In parallel, low-power device platforms require communication options aligned with the available energy budget. Backscatter devices and wake-up radio designs are essential because they allow sensing and connectivity with minimal active transmission. A systematic view of these options, together with updated life-cycle assessment of typical components, supports responsible design choices and quantifies environmental impact. The combination of EH, management, and ultra-low-power communication forms the technical driver of this deliverable.

1.3 Scope and Objectives

The scope of D2.2 is to document, analyze, and consolidate hardware solutions that enable autonomous operation of low-power devices across the device classes introduced in D2.1. The document concentrates on three layers of the physical stack. First, it surveys EH technologies, including characterization of commercial photovoltaic options and fundamentals of thermoelectric conversion, together with methods for forecasting harvesting potential that can guide protocol and duty-cycling decisions. Second, it details power transfer architectures and front ends, with an emphasis on radio frequency (RF) charge pumps, energy transmitter design, and comparative aspects of ambient versus dedicated RF harvesting. Third, it examines multisource power management, including energy combiners, supervisory functions, and protection mechanisms for safe and efficient storage use.

Complementing these foundations, the deliverable surveys device platforms and enabling modules for ultra-low-power communication, namely backscattering-type implementations and wake-up

Table 1.1: Summary of Deliverable D2.2.

Area	What D2.2 Adds	Impact on Subsequent Tasks
Energy harvesting and power transfer	Survey of light, thermal, vibration, and RF options; RF rectifiers and charge pumps; wireless power transfer with fixed and mobile transmitters; comparison of ambient and dedicated RF.	Sharper harvester selection; correct storage sizing; energy-aware duty cycles and protocol settings; deployment guidance for reliable operation.
Multisource power management	Combiner architectures; cold start and prioritization; protection mechanisms; energy balance monitoring with low quiescent consumption.	More robust service under variable sources; stable interfaces to radios, sensing, and compute; lower integration risk.
Low-power device platforms	Curated platforms with clear energy profiles and configuration options; measurement guidance for idle and active modes.	Faster platform selection; quicker first integration; reproducible measurements across prototypes.
Backscatter communication	Tag and reader options; hardware baselines; expected range envelopes by band and scenario.	Communication for energy-constrained nodes; reduced active radio time; improved service availability.
Wake-up radios	Front ends and lightweight detection; trigger design and filtering guidelines; coupling with the main radio kept simple.	Longer device lifetime; event-driven operation; lower communication overhead without loss of responsiveness.
Life-cycle assessment of components	Updated impact factors for boards, radios, processing, memory, storage, incoming energy, and casing; mapping from bill of materials to metrics.	Better material choices; support for sustainability indicators and procurement decisions.
Interfaces and traceability from D2.1	Mapping from classes and capability code to hardware blocks; selection workflow and checklists with clear interfaces.	Consistent bridge from taxonomy to implementation; smoother handover to integration, testing, and validation.

radio front ends and processing options. An updated life-cycle assessment is included to quantify the environmental impact of core components and to inform material and architecture choices. The objectives are to provide a consolidated reference for hardware blocks, to report measured or literature-based performance data, to identify integration interfaces between harvesters, power management, and radios, and to prepare a consistent input to subsequent design and validation tasks in the project. The focused areas, main contributions, and impact on subsequent technical tasks are summarized in Table 1.1.

1.4 Structure of the Document

The document is organized as follows.

- Chapter 2 presents fundamentals and practicalities of EH, power transfer, and multisource power management. It details the selection of energy harvesters, power management units, multisource combiners, energy balance monitors, and voltage limiting techniques.
- Chapter 3 focuses on low-power device platforms, backscattering-type devices, and wake-up radio design. It reports representative low-power devices, options for radio frequency identification (RFID)-based backscattering and related hardware, and wake-up front ends and processing considerations.
- Chapter 4 presents an updated life-cycle assessment of typical components and assemblies, including printed circuit boards, communication subsystems, memory, processing, energy storage, and incoming energy options, together with casing.
- Chapter 5 concludes the document.

Chapter 2

Energy Harvesting, Power Transfer, and Multisource Power Management Circuits

This chapter establishes the building blocks that turn intermittent energy into dependable service. It reviews ambient sources such as light, heat, vibration, and RF signals, and it introduces dedicated WPT when ambient supply is insufficient. For each source, we summarize conversion front ends, rectifiers, and charge pump options, together with link budget considerations. We then present multisource power management that combines harvesters, supervises cold start, prioritizes inputs, and protects storage and loads through voltage limiting and current control. We define interfaces between harvesters, storage, and the load, with emphasis on low-quiescent consumption and predictable transients, since those properties dominate service availability of low-power platforms.

2.1 Energy Harvesting

In this section, several EH techniques are introduced, such as using light EH, thermal EH, RF EH, as well as an energy-aware protocol switching in END via harvesting potential predictions.

2.1.1 Fundamentals, Types, and Characterization of Commercial Off-the-shelf Photovoltaic Cells for Light Energy Harvesting

In this subsection, an overview of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) PV cells employed for EH among END is presented. First, the principle of photovoltaic conversion and typical power output for moderate-sized panels are described. The main types of PV cells suitable for IoT applications are discussed in terms of materials, manufacturing processes, cost, market scale, and principal manufacturers. Subsequently, key performance parameters and related characteristics used to evaluate PV cells are introduced. The concept of simultaneous light information and power transfer (SLIPT) is then discussed, focusing on PV cell selection criteria and evaluation methods. Finally, the methodology adopted for experimental characterization of seven PV cells is detailed.

2.1.1.1 Overview and Principle of Photovoltaic Technology

Photovoltaic conversion relies on the photovoltaic effect, which generates a voltage and electric current in a semiconductor junction upon exposure to light [1]. When photons possessing energy exceeding the semiconductor bandgap are absorbed, electron-hole pairs are produced and separated by the built-in electric field of a p-n junction, leading to direct current generation [2]. Typical PV cells employ silicon as the semiconductor material, although alternative materials such as cadmium telluride (CDTE), copper indium gallium selenide (CIGS), perovskites, and organic polymers have been developed [3].

In IoT energy-harvesting scenarios, PV cells convert ambient illumination, either sunlight or artificial indoor lighting, into electrical power to sustain low-power sensor nodes and wireless transceivers [4]. The recommended illumination level for different area can be found in [5]. Under indoor illuminance levels ranging from 100 lx to 1000 lx, advanced indoor PV harvesters can deliver power densities on the order of tens to hundreds of $\mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$ [4]. Under full-sun outdoor conditions (approximately 1000 W m^{-2}), a moderate-sized panel with active area of 0.01 m^2 (for example, $10 \text{ cm} \times 10 \text{ cm}$) and an efficiency of 20% can produce roughly 2 W of electrical power [6]. This amount is sufficient to charge batteries or supercapacitors that supply duty-cycled IoT devices. The power output of a PV cell generally depends on incident irradiance G of light, cell temperature T , and cell efficiency η . The maximum output power of a PV cell can be expressed by

$$P_{\max} = \eta G A, \quad (2.1)$$

where A is the cell area. Cell temperature influences open-circuit voltage V_{oc} negatively and short-circuit current I_{sc} positively, yielding a net decrease in P_{\max} as temperature increases [3].

2.1.1.2 Typical Parameters of PV Cells

Electrical Parameters Photovoltaic cell performance is quantified by the current-voltage (I-V) characteristic under standard test conditions (STC: 1000 W m^{-2} , AM1.5G standard spectrum, 25°C). Key parameters include [3]:

- **Open-Circuit voltage** V_{oc} : the voltage at zero load current.
- **Short-Circuit Current** I_{sc} : the current at zero voltage.
- **Maximum Power Point** ($P_{\max} = V_{\text{mp}} I_{\text{mp}}$): the point on the I-V curve where the power is maximized, corresponding to voltage V_{mp} and current I_{mp} .
- **Fill Factor** (FF): defined as $\text{FF} = \frac{V_{\text{mp}} I_{\text{mp}}}{V_{\text{oc}} I_{\text{sc}}}$, indicating the “squareness” of the I-V curve.
- **Power Conversion Efficiency** η : ratio of P_{\max} to incident power GA .

Spectral and Responsivity Parameters Spectral responsivity $R(\lambda)$ defines the photocurrent generated per unit incident optical power at wavelength λ . Quantum efficiency [1], [7] $\text{QE}(\lambda)$ is related to responsivity by $\text{QE}(\lambda) = \frac{\lambda R(\lambda)}{hc/e}$, where h is Planck’s constant, c is the speed of light, and e is the elementary charge. Indoor PV materials are optimized for visible wavelengths (400 nm to 700 nm), whereas outdoor PV materials target the solar spectrum peak near 1000 nm.

Table 2.1: Brief comparison of photovoltaic technologies relevant to energy harvesting.

Technology	Outdoor efficiency	Indoor performance	Flexibility	Cost and maturity	Typical uses
Crystalline silicon	15–24 %	Moderate at 200–1000 lx	Rigid	Very low cost; very mature	Utility, rooftop, outdoor IoT
Thin-film	10–13 %	Good at low lux	Rigid or flexible	Low cost; mature for CdTe/CIGS	BIPV, façades, indoor IoT
Perovskite and DSSC	Evolving; fast progress	High at 500–1000 lx	Thin; potentially flexible	Low-cost potential; stability limits	Indoor harvesters, prototypes
Organic	Lower than c-Si/CdTe	10–20 $\mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$ at 500 lx	Very flexible; lightweight	Low materials cost; emerging	Wearables, conformal, indoor

2.1.1.3 Types of Photovoltaic Cells for IoT Devices

Global PV module shipments exceeded 500 GW in 2024, dominated by leading manufacturers such as JinkoSolar, JA Solar, LONGi, Trina Solar, and Canadian Solar [8]. Tier-1 manufacturers typically produce modules at $\$0.20 \text{ W}^{-1}$ to 0.30 W^{-1} in 2025, with large economies of scale reducing costs substantially [9]. Emerging IoT-specific PV suppliers include PowerFilm, Anysolar, and Ambient Photonics [10], [11]. A comparison of PV cell technologies are shown in Table 2.1 and are introduced in the sequel.

Silicon-Based PV Cells Crystalline silicon (c-Si) PV cells are the most prevalent, including monocrystalline and polycrystalline variants [3]. Monocrystalline cells exhibit higher efficiencies (19–24 %) than polycrystalline cells (15–18 %) due to superior crystalline quality [6]. Silicon wafer fabrication employs the Czochralski or float-zone processes, followed by doping, diffusion, and metallization steps. Module assembly involves encapsulation under ethylene-vinyl acetate and mounting on glass or polymer substrates. The levelized cost of silicon PV cells has decreased to below $\$0.15 \text{ W}^{-1}$ for large-scale production, with polysilicon feedstock and wafer manufacturing representing major cost components [12]. Leading manufacturers of c-Si modules include JinkoSolar, JA Solar, Trina Solar, LONGi, Canadian Solar, Hanwha Qcells, and ANYSOLAR [9].

Thin-Film PV Cells Thin-film technologies, such as amorphous silicon (a-Si), CDTE, and CIGS, offer lower production costs and mechanical flexibility at the expense of lower conversion efficiency. Amorphous silicon cells are deposited via plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition, while CDTE and CIGS are typically sputtered or co-evaporated onto glass or flexible substrates [12]. Typical efficiencies for thin-film cells range from 10–13 % in module form. First Solar and Solar Frontier are key manufacturers of such PV cells. Thin-film modules are used for building-integrated photovoltaics and indoor light harvesting due to superior low-light performance [13].

Perovskite and Dye-Sensitized PV Cells Perovskite solar cells utilize organic-inorganic halide perovskite absorbers (e.g., $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$) deposited via solution processing [14]. Indoor perovskite PV devices with bandgaps near 1.75 eV can achieve power conversion efficiencies up to 25 % under 1000 lx illumination [15]. Perovskite solar cell fabrication employs spin coating, doctor blading (blade coating), or vapor deposition followed by low-temperature annealing, enabling flexible and low-cost modules. Dye-sensitized solar cells use mesoporous TiO_2 with adsorbed

dye molecules and an electrolyte; their efficiency under indoor lighting can exceed 20 % in small modules [16]. Commercialization remains limited due to stability concerns.

Organic PV Cells Organic PV cells employ semiconducting polymers and small molecules as active layers, fabricated by roll-to-roll printing on flexible substrates [4]. Indoor organic PV cell can deliver 10–20 $\mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$ at 500 lx, with power conversion efficiencies of up to 21 % under controlled indoor illumination [4]. Major organic PV cell suppliers include Heliatek and FlexEnable. Organic PV cells exhibit low cost and mechanical flexibility but remain susceptible to photochemical degradation.

2.1.1.4 PV Cells for SLIPT

Apart from using PV cells for EH purpose, SLIPT technique integrates visible light communication with photovoltaic EH. This technique uses optical transmitters, such as a light emitting diode or laser diode, to modulate data onto a lightwave while simultaneously supplying energy to the receiver PV cell. In such configuration, the PV cell alternates between a photoconductive mode for information decoding and a photovoltaic mode for EH. Receiver architectures for SLIPT are generally classified as: (i) time-splitting, where time slots are alternated between EH and data reception; (ii) power-splitting, where a fraction of the optical power is diverted to a photodetector for information while the remainder is used by the PV cell for power generation; (iii) adaptive reception, which employs real-time adjustment of PV bias and load conditions to optimize the trade-off between communication and energy metrics. Hybrid designs may combine a high-bandwidth photodetector for data demodulation with a PV element tuned for maximum direct current (DC) conversion.

The selection of PV cells for SLIPT applications should be guided by several key criteria. First, broad spectral responsivity in the visible band is required to ensure sufficient photocurrent for both EH and data detection. Second, high energy conversion efficiency is needed to maximize the harvested DC power under given illumination conditions. Third, low parasitic capacitance and resistance are imperative to achieve high-speed modulation and to raise the RC cutoff frequency. Fourth, rapid photodetection response, with nanosecond-scale rise and fall times, is essential for high data-rate applications. Finally, stability of open-circuit voltage and short-circuit current under high-frequency optical modulation should be ensured to prevent performance degradation during simultaneous operation. Evaluation of candidate PV cells is thus carried out through measurement of frequency response, bandwidth, alternating current (AC) amplitude transfer characteristics, and DC energy conversion under modulated illumination.

2.1.1.5 Experimental Characterization of COTS PV Cells

Test Samples Seven models of COTS PV cells from ANYSOLAR are selected for characterization because of their widespread use in light energy-harvesting END prototypes, as shown in Fig. 2.1. The models are listed in Table 2.2 with key parameters provided by the vendor [17].

Throughout the table, it is observed that within the “K12L” family, increasing the unit-cell width from 10.8 mm to 21.5 mm nearly doubled the short-circuit current (from 21.0 mA to 41.9 mA) and correspondingly increased the maximum power from 132.3 mW to 263.0 mW, illustrating that wider unit cells capture more photons at the expense of larger package size and weight. Modules with different series counts (4, 9, or 12 cells) are found to enable nominal voltage

Figure 2.1: Tested 7 PV cells samples (left) and characterization measurement setup (right).

Table 2.2: Specifications of tested PV Cells provided by manufacturer.

No.	Model	V_{oc} (V)	I_{sc} (mA)	P_{max} (mW)	V_{max} (V)	I_{max} (mA)	FF (%)	Efficiency (%)	ΔV_{oc} (mV)	ΔI_{sc} (mA)	Dimension (mm)	Weight (g)	Unit Cell (mm)	Cells in Series
1	KXOB12IK04TF	2.76	50.2	105.3	2.23	47.2	> 70	25	-6.96	0.0227	23 × 25 × 1.2	1.2	21.5 × 5.65 × 1	4
2	SM500K12L	8.29	21.0	132.3	6.70	19.8	> 70	25	-20.9	0.0095	24 × 32 × 1.8	2.5	10.8 × 4.71 × 1	12
3	SM710K12L	8.29	29.2	183.7	6.70	27.4	> 70	25	-20.9	0.0100	32.5 × 33 × 1.8	4.5	15.0 × 4.71 × 1	12
4	SM850K12L	8.29	35.1	221.0	6.70	32.9	> 70	25	-20.9	0.0159	38.5 × 33 × 1.8	4.3	18.0 × 4.71 × 1	12
5	SM101K12L	8.29	41.9	263.0	6.70	39.3	> 70	25	-20.9	0.0189	45 × 32 × 1.8	4.8	21.5 × 4.71 × 1	12
6	SM141K04LV	2.76	58.6	123.0	2.23	55.1	> 70	25	-7.00	0.0265	45 × 15 × 1.8	2.3	21.5 × 6.80 × 1	4
7	SM111K09L	6.22	46.7	220.4	5.02	43.9	> 70	25	-15.7	0.0200	62 × 21 × 1.8	5.5	20.0 × 5.65 × 1	9

targeting for downstream power management: four-cell modules provide approximately 2.7 V, suitable for low-voltage converters, whereas twelve-cell strings yield about 8.3 V, appropriate for boost-converter inputs. Four-cell K04 modules achieved high short-circuit current (50–58 mA) in a compact footprint, producing P_{max} values comparable to those of smaller-area twelve-cell modules due to reduced series resistance, although voltage step-up is required for loads above 2.2 V. The specified tolerances in open-circuit voltage (-6.96 mV to -20.9 mV) and short-circuit current (0.0095–0.0265 mA) suggest that K12L cells experience slightly greater V_{oc} drift under environmental variations, while all modules demonstrate robust current-output stability under moderate indoor lighting.

A uniform 25 % efficiency rating across unit cells indicates a consistent semiconductor technology, but real-world performance will be governed by spectral mismatch, temperature coefficients, and series-resistance losses. From an SLIPT perspective, all cells feature fill factors above 70 % and substantial unit-cell areas that support both DC power harvesting and AC data reception; four-cell modules are expected to offer the highest modulation bandwidth due to lower total junction capacitance, whereas twelve-cell devices maximize harvested energy at the cost of reduced high-frequency response.

Measurement Setup However, for above PV cells, key performance metrics related to SLIPT, such as AC response, DC response, and bandwidth are not provided by the vendor, which need to be systematically measured and analyzed. The measurement setup for the PV cell characterization is displayed in Fig. 2.1. The intensity modulation/direct detection method is utilized for light modulation. A functional generator (Tektronix AFG31000) produces a sine-wave electrical signal with an amplitude of 3 V, at frequencies ranging from 1–100 kHz, which modulates a light emitting diode (LED) driver biased by an 21 V DC power supply. A general purpose 7-LED module (OSRAM GW J9LHS2.4M-C0C7-2+35+13+35AW-1-100-R18) emits the modulated optical signal with the visible light spectrum from 400–800 nm. The optical output illuminated each PV

Figure 2.2: Magnitude of PV-output AC components V_{AC} for all PV cells in terms of the varying light-modulating frequencies, at different distances between the LED and PV cell.

Figure 2.3: Comparison of the PV-output AC components across all tested PV cells, for different distances (0.5 m, 0.4 m, 0.3 m, and 0.2 m) between the LED and PV cells.

cell under test, respectively. For each sample, both AC (peak-to-peak) and DC (mean) output of the photovoltaic-converted signal are recorded simultaneously by an oscilloscope (Rohde & Schwarz RTO64). All measurements are conducted in a darkened enclosure to eliminate ambient light interference. All measurement are repeated twice. Moreover, a ThorLabs PDA100A2 silicon photodetector is employed as a high-performance photodetector benchmark [18], featuring a bandwidth of 11 MHz. The subsequent paragraphs present and analyze the AC and DC response, bandwidth, and its correlation with manufacturer-rated output power.

AC Response and Bandwidth Fig. 2.2 presents the measured magnitude of AC components V_{AC} for all PV cells in terms of the varying light-modulating frequencies. For the measurement among each PV cell, different distances d between the LED and PV cell are adopted, ranging from 0.2 m to 0.5 m. A band-pass shape is observed for all PV cells: the magnitude rises from the lowest frequency, peaks between 3 kHz and 8 kHz, and thereafter decays with an approximate -20 dB dec^{-1} slope towards 100 kHz. The trend is in close agreement with the small-signal RC model of a junction photovoltaic cell, where the dynamic resistance R_{pv} dominates at low frequency and the junction capacitance C_{pv} dominates at high frequency. The analytic corner

Figure 2.4: Magnitude of PV-output DC components V_{DC} for all PV cells in terms of the varying light-modulating frequencies, at different distances between the LED and PV cell.

frequency is

$$f_c = \frac{1}{2\pi R_{pv} C_{pv}}, \quad (2.2)$$

and the experimentally extracted f_{3dB} values follow this proportionality. Four-cell modules reach $f_{3dB} \approx 20$ kHz because the total junction capacitance is the smallest. Nine-cell devices attain 14–16 kHz, while twelve-cell strings exhibit the lowest bandwidth, from 2 kHz for the smallest cell area to 17 kHz for the largest area. Reducing the distance between the LED and PV cell from 0.5 m to 0.2 m raises the incident photon flux. It can be seen that V_{AC} scales almost linearly with distance. For comparison, the benchmark photodetector produces a flat response up to 40 kHz and then rolls off, indicating that the experimental apparatus have small effect on the observed PV bandwidth.

Fig. 2.3 compares the AC output of all tested PV cells at each LED-PV distance d . At $d = 0.5$ m, the midband amplitudes span approximately 0.5–3.7 mV, with PV-1 (four-cell) leading and PV-2 (twelve-cell smallest area) trailing. As d is reduced to 0.4 m and 0.3 m, the overall envelope of V_{AC} increases in proportion to irradiance, yet the ranking of devices remains unchanged: four-cell modules always exhibit the highest amplitudes and twelve-cell modules the lowest, with intermediate performance from the nine-cell device. At the closest distance $d = 0.2$ m the peak AC outputs approach 15 mV for PV-1 and 12 mV for PV-7 (nine-cell), while the smallest twelve-cell cell remains below 6 mV. Across all distances, the peak response occurs between 3 kHz and 6 kHz, after which a monotonic roll-off is observed. This consistency confirms that device-intrinsic parameters, namely junction capacitance and series resistance, dictate the midband amplitude and high-frequency attenuation, whereas the optical intensity merely scales the magnitude of V_{AC} .

DC Response Fig. 2.4 shows that the output DC voltage V_{DC} of each PV module is nearly invariant with modulation frequency. Across the entire 1–100 kHz sweep, the variation remains below five millivolts, much smaller than the step caused by distance. This confirms that energy-

Figure 2.5: Comparison of the PV-output DC components across all tested PV cells, for different distances (0.5 m, 0.4 m, 0.3 m, and 0.2 m) between the LED and PV cells.

Figure 2.6: Measured 3-dB bandwidth of PV cells at different distances between the LED and PV cells.

harvesting capability is rarely penalized by data modulation in the considered range. Furthermore, the output DC levels separate the cells into three groups. Four-cell devices harvest the highest voltage (up to 30 mV at 0.2 m) because each unit cell is large and the series string is short. Nine-cell devices harvest moderately less, whereas twelve-cell devices span a wide range that correlates strongly with the unit-cell area. The hierarchy is preserved over distance, proving that geometry rather than intensity governs the ordering. The PD yields a DC voltage that sits mid-range because it is optimized for responsivity rather than power extraction.

Fig. 2.5 compares the DC output of all tested PV cells at different distances. In every sub-plot, V_{DC} is almost invariant with modulation frequency for most of PV cells, confirming that carrier modulation up to 100 kHz does not perturb the harvested DC. At $d = 0.5$ m the DC voltages span approximately 0.8–3.1 mV, reflecting the series-cell count and unit-cell area. As d decreases, all curves shift upward in proportion to the incident irradiance (approximately $1/d^2$), yet their relative ordering remains unchanged: four-cell modules yield the highest V_{DC} (e.g., for PV-6: $V_{DC} \approx 30$ mV at 0.2 m), nine-cell modules are next, and twelve-cell strings deliver the lowest voltages. This consistency demonstrates that EH is governed by PV cell geometry and illumination level rather than by the presence of high-frequency light modulation.

Bandwidth Fig. 2.6 presents the measured 3-dB bandwidth f_{3dB} of PV cells 1 through 7 at four LED-PV distances $d = 0.5$ m, 0.4 m, 0.3 m, and 0.2 m, respectively. At the lowest irradiance ($d = 0.5$ m), the smallest PV cell (PV-1) exhibits a modest bandwidth of approximately 1.2 kHz,

Figure 2.7: Measured 3-dB bandwidth of PV cells versus vendor specified maximum output power P_{\max} .

while larger cells reach between 9 kHz and 16.5 kHz. As the distance is reduced to $d = 0.2$ m, the bandwidth of PV-1 increases markedly to about 13 kHz, whereas cells 2-7 show only minor changes (± 1.5 kHz), indicating that above a threshold photon flux their intrinsic capacitance and series resistance govern the cutoff frequency. Among the larger-area modules, the nine-cell device (PV-7) and the largest twelve-cell module (PV-5) achieve the highest bandwidths (approx. 16–17 kHz), mid-sized twelve-cell modules (PV-3 and PV-4) reach 13–15 kHz, and the smallest twelve-cell module (PV-2) remains below 10 kHz. This ordering reflects the inverse relationship between total junction capacitance and achievable bandwidth. The data imply that PV-7 or PV-5 should be selected for SLIPT purpose requiring symbol rates above 15 kHz, whereas PV-2 or PV-6 may sufficient when EH is prioritized over data rate.

The manufacturer specifies a maximum power P_{\max} under one-sun illumination for each PV device. When the experimental $f_{3\text{dB}}$ values are plotted against P_{\max} , as shown in Fig. 2.7, where a monotonic increase is visible. A cubic fit captures the empirical trend by $f_{3\text{dB}} = 0.015 P_{\max}^3 - 9.21 P_{\max}^2 + 1.86 \times 10^3 P_{\max} - 1.07 \times 10^5$, where $f_{3\text{dB}}$ is in hertz and P_{\max} in milliwatts. The positive slope confirms that higher-power cells, which possess larger active areas and lower series resistances, inherently support wider communication bandwidth.

Several insights are obtained from the above characterization measurements. The AC response of each PV module exhibits an RC-limited band-pass profile with peaks between 3 kHz and 8 kHz, indicating that the electronic time constant rather than the optical path governs the bandwidth. The measured 3-dB bandwidth is remarkably stable across a four-fold variation in irradiance (LED-PV distance from 0.5 m to 0.2 m), changing by no more than ten percent. Bandwidth is found to increase systematically with both reduced series cell count and higher manufacturer-reported P_{\max} , and the empirical cubic fit derived herein provides a first-order predictor for untested modules. In parallel, the DC output remains unaffected by modulation frequencies up to 100 kHz, confirming that EH and data transfer can coexist without mutual degradation. These findings imply that no single PV module optimizes all performance metrics simultaneously; instead, selection should be guided by the specific data-rate and energy-harvesting requirements of the target application.

Figure 2.8: Basic structure of a TEG, showing four thermocouples connected electrically in series and thermally in parallel. A temperature gradient across the device induces a voltage via the Seebeck effect, causing a current to flow through the load resistor R_L .

2.1.2 Fundamentals of Thermoelectric Generators for Thermal Energy Harvesting

Thermal gradients present in industrial, environmental, or wearable contexts can be exploited as a continuous power source for low-power devices.

2.1.2.1 Working Principle of TEGs

TEGs enable direct conversion of heat into electricity, leveraging the intrinsic transport properties of thermoelectric materials: thermal conductivity, electrical conductivity, and Seebeck coefficient. These materials can convert thermal energy into electrical energy and vice versa, depending on the direction of energy flow.

- When electrical energy is converted into thermal energy, the phenomenon is called the *Peltier effect*, with applications in solid state heating and cooling.
- When thermal energy is converted into electrical energy, the phenomenon is called the *Seebeck effect*, which is the primary mechanism exploited in the harvesting of thermoelectric energy. This effect will be the focus of this section.

The Seebeck effect occurs when a temperature difference across a conductor or semiconductor induces a voltage between its ends. This voltage arises from the diffusion of charge carriers (electrons in n -type materials, holes in p -type materials) in response to the thermal gradient.

The basic structure of a TEG is shown in Figure 2.8 [19]. A TEG consists of multiple thermocouples, each made up of a pair of n -type and p -type thermoelectric legs. These legs are connected electrically in series and thermally in parallel. The p -type leg has a positive Seebeck coefficient, while the n -type leg has a negative one. When these legs are joined by a conducting strip (typically copper), a voltage is developed across the device terminals. Connecting an electrical load to these terminals allows current to flow, thereby generating electrical power.

A TEG continues to produce DC power as long as a temperature difference $\Delta T = T_{\text{hot}} - T_{\text{cold}}$ is maintained across its surfaces. A higher ΔT results in a higher output voltage and thus power.

Figure 2.9: Basic electrical equivalent circuit of a thermoelectric generator. The TEG is modeled as a voltage source in series with an internal resistance, delivering power to a load resistor R_L .

The TEG can be represented by a basic equivalent electrical circuit, which models the device as a voltage source in series with an internal resistance (as shown in Figure 2.9) [20]. The voltage source represents the open-circuit voltage induced by the temperature gradient across the thermocouples, and the internal resistance represents the electrical resistance of the thermoelectric materials and interconnections. As such, the output power of a TEG can be expressed as:

$$P_{\text{out}} = I_{\text{out}}V_{\text{out}} = \alpha\Delta T I_{\text{out}} - I_{\text{out}}^2 R_m \quad (2.3)$$

Due to the presence of the internal resistance R_m , the power delivered to the load depends not only on the temperature gradient but also on the electrical matching between the TEG and the load. The output power is maximized when the load resistance R_L is equal to the internal resistance R_m . Power management circuits designed to operate with TEGs need to operate near this optimal point for the most efficient power harvesting.

2.1.2.2 Integration into Energy Neutral (EN) IoT Devices

When selecting a TEG for any END IoT application, both the thermal and electrical characteristics of the TEG should be considered, as well as the supporting power management architecture. Several key parameters influence the suitability of a TEG:

- Temperature differential range: The TEG should operate efficiently under the expected ambient and surface temperature conditions.
- Seebeck coefficient (α): A higher coefficient allows the TEG to generate more voltage for a given temperature gradient.
- Internal electrical resistance (R_m): Lower internal resistance minimizes resistive losses and improves energy transfer efficiency.
- Thermal impedance and form factor: The TEG's thermal and mechanical integration into the system must allow for efficient heat flow. To sustain a temperature gradient across the device, a substantial heatsink is often required on the cold side, which may influence the overall device dimensions and placement.
- Power output under nominal conditions: The output power must be sufficient to meet the energy budget of the END, accounting for duty-cycling and sleep states.

ID	MPN	Dimensions	N_{pairs}	ID	MPN	Dimensions [mm]	N_{pairs}
1	GM200-127-10-15	30x30x3.7	127	11	GM250-161-12-40	40x40x6.8	161
2	GM200-127-28-12	62x62x4	127	12	GM200-161-12-20	40x40x4.2	161
3	GM200-127-28-10	62x62x4	127	13	GM250-161-12-20	40x40x4.2	161
4	GM250-127-10-15	30x30x3.7	127	14	GM250-241-10-16	40x40x3.4	241
5	GM250-127-28-12	62x62x4	127	15	GM200-241-10-12	40x40x3.4	241
6	GM250-127-28-10	62x62x4	127	16	GM250-241-10-12	40x40x3.4	241
7	GM200-127-14-16	40x40x3.4	127	17	GM200-31-14-10	20x20x3	31
8	GM200-127-14-10	40x40x3.4	127	18	GM200-31-28-35	30x30x6.3	31
9	GM250-127-14-10	40x40x3.4	127	19	GM250-31-28-35	30x30x6.3	31
10	GM200-161-12-40	40x40x6.8	161	20	GM250-31-14-10	20x20x3	31

Figure 2.10: Calculated maximum power point (P_{max} and V_{max}) for multiple commercial TEG modules of European Thermodynamics, for $T_{hot} = 70^{\circ}C$ and $T_{cold} = 30^{\circ}C$

Fig. 2.10 shows the maximum output power and corresponding voltage for a selection of representative TEGs, calculated from their datasheet parameters (number of thermocouples, leg dimensions, internal resistance, and Seebeck coefficients) under a temperature difference of $\Delta T = 50^\circ\text{C}$. These results represent the peak achievable power under matched conditions for this ΔT . Typical TEGs operating under lower and more irregular temperature gradients produce output voltages in the range of tens to hundreds of millivolts and power levels in the low milliwatt range. Consequently, a highly efficient ultra-low-voltage boost (or flyback) converter is used to boost the voltage to usable levels (e.g., 1.8–3.3 V).

Furthermore, because the instantaneous power available from a TEG is generally insufficient to support continuous operation of an END device, especially during communication events, buffering of harvested energy is necessary. After boosting, the energy is typically stored in a supercapacitor or rechargeable battery, which can then supply short bursts of higher current when required. This energy storage element also helps decouple the load from the variability of the thermal environment.

2.1.3 Charge Pumps for Radio Frequency-Energy Harvesting

In Ambient Internet of Things (A-IoT) devices, RF EH has emerged as a compelling solution to provide power, thereby eliminating batteries and supplementing other ambient energy sources. Central to this approach are charge pump architectures, which convert low-amplitude, high-frequency AC signals into usable DC voltages. Unlike conventional rectifiers, which suffer from threshold voltage losses and limited voltage gain, charge pumps not only rectify but also multiply the input voltage through cascaded capacitive stages. This voltage multiplication is essential for achieving sufficient output levels under weak RF excitation, often below -20 dBm , and enables cold-start operation from input voltages as low as 100–200 mV [21].

Two classical topologies, the Villard and the Dickson charge pumps, are frequently employed in EH designs. While both utilize capacitive coupling and diode-like switching elements, the Dickson topology offers superior performance due to its re-connection of each stage to the input terminals, reducing voltage drop and improving output swing [22], [23]. These designs are illustrated in Fig. 2.11, and can be extended to multi-stage configurations to meet specific voltage and power requirements.

To overcome the limitations of diode-connected rectifiers, modern charge pump designs leverage complementary metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) technology and implement threshold voltage compensation techniques such as gate boosting and bulk biasing. These methods reduce the effective threshold voltage V_{TH} of the rectifying transistors, allowing operation in the subthreshold domain and improving power conversion efficiency (PCE). A typical multi-stage RF-DC charge pump consists of rectifying transistors and coupling capacitors, as shown in Fig. 2.12 [24].

Differential charge pump architectures are particularly advantageous in ambient RF EH. They offer improved noise immunity, enable direct antenna integration without baluns, and allow full-wave rectification by utilizing both positive and negative halves of the input signal. Zöscher et al. [25] demonstrated a differential charge pump with integrated auxiliary biasing circuits that generate gate and bulk voltages internally. This design, fabricated in a 40 nm CMOS process, achieved a PCE of 42.7% at -20.3 dBm input power, delivering $4\text{ }\mu\text{W}$ at 1 V output. The input quality factor Q remained below 14, enabling broadband impedance matching and robust operation under parasitic loading.

Figure 2.11: Villard and Dickson charge pump (voltage multiplier) circuit topology. Both multipliers consist of two stages, which could be expanded with additional stages to achieve the desired output voltage [23].

Figure 2.12: Differential multi-stage charge pump with gate and bulk biasing [24].

Recent work by Poehl et al. [26] extended this architecture to the 2.45 GHz industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) band, demonstrating that even legacy designs optimized for 900 MHz can perform efficiently at higher frequencies. The test integrated circuit (IC) achieved a PCE of 25.9% and a sensitivity of -18.3 dBm at 1 V output, validating its suitability for ambient harvesting from wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi) and Bluetooth signals. Table 2.3 compares this work with other state-of-the-art implementations.

In summary, charge pumps are a cornerstone of RF EH systems for ultra-low power IoT applications. Innovations in topology, threshold voltage management, and impedance matching have enabled significant improvements in efficiency and startup performance. Differential architectures with integrated biasing circuits represent a key advancement, offering high sensitivity, robust operation, and compatibility with modern CMOS processes. These developments pave

Table 2.3: Comparison table showcasing the results of the presented charge pump design alongside related studies, highlighting power conversion efficiency and realized sensitivity at a DC output voltage of 1 V [23].

	Year	Frequency (GHz)	PCE (%)	P_{in} (dBm)	Sensitivity (dBm)	Technology
Soltani [27]	2010	2.40	2.7	-12.0	-12.0	180 nm dual half-wave rectifier
Heo [28]	2021	2.40	67.1	-12.0	-17.0	65 nm dual-stage charge-pump
Basim [29]	2022	2.40	26.5	-6.0	-16.0	180 nm threshold voltage cancellation charge-pump
Lian [30]	2023	2.40	32.0	0.0	-13.2	65 nm Dickson charge-pump
Yong [31]	2023	2.40	30.4	-10.0	-20.0	65 nm 6-stage charge-pump
Poehl [26]	2025	2.45	25.9	-4.6	-18.3	40 nm 8-stage charge-pump

the way for scalable, battery-free, and energy-autonomous systems that can harvest ambient RF energy from ubiquitous wireless infrastructure.

Efficient use of RF EH Energy While charge pump architectures form the physical foundation for ambient RF energy harvesting in A-IoT devices, their integration into system-level energy management strategies is equally critical. The harvested energy must be intelligently allocated to communication tasks, especially in multi-radio access technology (RAT) environments where protocol selection impacts both energy consumption and communication performance.

2.1.4 Multi-Radio Access Technology Energy Neutral Device Modem Capability - Implications for Networking & Energy Harvesting

Data forwarding by A-IoT devices can be performed over a particular RAT that is supported by both the particular A-IoT device and the data sink (e.g., a multi-access edge computing (MEC) host that is access-agnostic by definition). Each RAT, such as narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) or long range (LoRa) is characterized by its own frequency bands, modulation schemes, protocol stacks and coverage and capacity characteristics.

Multi-RAT IoT devices (e.g., enabling communication via NB-IoT and LoRa RATs) are technically feasible and increasingly common in advanced use cases. These devices can include multiple radio front-ends and baseband processors, each supporting a specific RAT. The most appropriate RAT can be selected at each time, based on the device's energy availability, cov-

Figure 2.13: Adaptive operation of an END supporting multiple RAT communication modules (modems).

erage, quality-of-service (QoS) requirements, and application context. Such RAT adaptation capability is particularly useful in scenarios of single-RAT availability, e.g., fallback to NB-IoT when LoRa is unavailable, or energy-aware communication (e.g., using LoRa at times when device battery level is low).

Shifting to ENDS capable of harvesting ambient RF energy, the EH quality (i.e., power density, harvesting volatility in time and in space) differs depending on the RAT used by devices and access nodes operating in proximity to the END performing EH. This happens because the amount and availability of the RF energy to be harvested is influenced by the frequency band of the RAT, the transmission power and duty cycle of nearby transmitters, the characteristics of the waveform used, and the distance from the RF source. As an example, as LoRa operates in sub-GHz bands, it may offer longer harvesting range, thus, more stable energy at the cost of lower power density, whereas, fifth-generation (5G)-New Radio (NR) and Wi-Fi can offer higher power density but signaling is more bursty and less predictable.

Thanks to the modular hardware architecture of an END with RF-EH capability, such END does not need to have the modem of that RAT activated in order to harvest RF energy relating to that RAT, as RF EH is typically decoupled from the communication modem. EH circuits (e.g., rectennas) are passive and can absorb RF energy regardless of whether the END is actively communicating. Hence, the END can harvest energy from any ambient RF source, even if it does not support that RAT for communication. As a result, an END may harvest energy from, e.g., 5G-NR base stations (BSs) and Wi-Fi access points (APs) and use that energy to power a low duty-cycle sensor for subsequent data transmission via LoRa or NB-IoT depending on the RATs it supports. Of course, the same approach can be applied in case the END has other or subsequent EH capabilities besides RF EH.

Adaptive RAT switching can rely on present EH potential or this potential can be predicted

in advance. The prediction-based approach has the benefit of providing to the END the time needed to activate the transceiver supporting the RAT that is both available in the geographical area of focus and, at the same time, less energy-consuming, taking into account the predicted EH opportunities in space and in time. In that case, the adaptation steps will be as follows: (i) the END or a network infrastructure entity (e.g., a prediction function within a MEC host) predicts ambient energy availability (across RATs regarding RF-EH) in the area and time of interest of the requesting END, (ii) the END monitors its current energy storage level, (iii) if both the predicted EH potential and current END energy storage level are low, the END switches to a low-power RAT, such as LoRa. On the contrary, if the predicted EH potential is high and current END energy storage level are sufficient, the END will switch to a higher-throughput RAT, such as NB-IoT. Figure 2.13 illustrates the proposed adaptive approach by means of activating/ deactivating END communication components.

2.2 Radio Frequency Wireless Power Transfer

Radio frequency wireless power transmission (RF WPT) is a promising solution for energy-sustainable wireless networks, enabling continuous operation of ENDS without battery replacement or wired charging. Its end-to-end (E2E) efficiency, however, is constrained by propagation losses, rectifier non-linearities, and hardware limitations at both the transmitter and receiver sides. On the transmitter side, advanced energy transmitter (ET) architectures can deliver highly directive beams, extend coverage, and reduce hardware cost and complexity. On the receiver side, concurrent RF EH from both dedicated and ambient signals requires flexible circuit designs capable of handling wide input power ranges while maintaining high conversion efficiency. In addition, energy delivery through unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) offers a complementary solution for powering remote or hard-to-reach devices. Together, these advances are paving the way toward efficient, scalable, and adaptive RF WPT networks.

2.2.1 Energy Transmitter Architectures

Physically large aperture arrays have become an attractive solution to boost power transfer end-to-end conversion efficiency and enable precise energy beam control in both depth and angular domains [32]. Fig. 2.14 illustrates emerging architectures based on lens antenna arrays, dynamic metasurface antennas, reflective intelligent surface (RIS)-equipped ET, movable antennas (MAs), and distributed antenna systems (DAS). These hold great potential to reduce the number of RF chains and minimize power consumption, complexity, and cost. For instance, lens arrays apply spatially varying phase shifts across their aperture to focus incoming electromagnetic waves from different angles onto distinct ports [33]–[35]. It transforms the spatial multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) channel into a sparse beamspace representation, which therefore requires fewer active RF chains [36]. Moreover, true-time-delay lens architectures, such as Rotman lenses, inherently provide passive retrodirectivity by reversing the phase profile of an incoming signal without requiring active phase shifters or complex feed networks [37]. Notably, their discrete implementation can limit angle-of-arrival (AOA) estimation accuracy, which can be improved by exploiting phase differences across adjacent elements [38]. RIS-equipped transmitters comprised a collocated digital fed beamformer illuminating a reconfigurable aperture that transmits and reflects a phase-shifted version of the impinging signal [39]. It replaces the traditional analog network with an air interface. The added spatial flexibility of RIS can be

Figure 2.14: ET architectures with physically large aperture arrays.

leveraged to implement both single- [40] and multi-RF chains [41] ETs. These advantages can be further exploited through joint waveform-beamforming co-design [42] and even utilize more advanced apertures based on beyond diagonal RIS [43], [44]. Finally, dynamic metasurface antennas consist of densely packed, sub-wavelength-spaced reconfigurable metamaterial elements that, through individual tuning, perform analog signal-processing functions directly in the aperture, eliminating the need for dedicated circuitry. Beamforming design for such ETs has been investigated for both maximizing harvested energy [45] and minimizing power consumption in signal transmission [46], [47], while joint beamforming and waveform optimization is studied in [48].

Movable antennas is an alternative ET architecture, wherein radiation patterns are modified via large-scale physical array reconfiguration. Their value lies in that they do not need a large number of antennas but rather a reduced set of them that can transmit from different points of the transmitter aperture. In the context of power transfer, the spatial flexibility of MAs can help mitigating the double near-far problem [49], boosting the received power [50], and supporting diverse service requirements [51]. Notably, the varying aperture of MAs to adjust to the varying channel conditions/active ENDS positions can impact near/far-field operation [52]. Finally, these degrees of freedom can be added to traditional antenna arrays to boost the received power in non-line-of-sight (NLoS) scenarios with strict electromagnetic radiation constraints [53].

Finally, DAS coordinates the transmissions of multiple radio heads implemented as low-complexity ETs, which can be deployed either as conventional arrays or through the aforementioned scalable architectures, as shown in Fig. 2.14. Convenient deployment and beamforming optimization of DAS extends power transfer coverage by reducing the charging distance and avoiding blockage in the service area [54], [55]. Practical implementations of DAS, such as the 280-antenna testbed in [56], have facilitated real-world evaluation of synchronization requirements [57], infrastructure architectures [58], and waveform and protocol design [59].

Figure 2.15: Advanced RF EH architectures based on (i) tunable (left), (ii) wide range dynamic range (center), and (iii) hybrid RF-DC combining (right) rectifiers.

2.2.2 Energy Harvesting Circuits Design for Radio Frequency Wireless Power Transmission

By enabling a dual RF EH mode, ENDS can prioritize RF EH from ambient transmissions and only request dedicated power transfer services if needed; thereby, saving energy at the ETs. In fact, ambient RF EH can be seen as a backup, if available, to meet minimum service guarantees when power transfer momentarily degrades. Note that in both cases ENDS can benefit from highly reliable operation while saving energy at the ETs. However, concurrent RF EH from ambient and dedicated transmissions requires flexible circuit designs to account for the different demands on receiver operation. As shown in Fig. 2.15 (left and center), such advance control can be enabled by machine learning (ML)-driven central-processing units (CPUs) to intelligently switch between ambient and dedicated RF EH, optimizing overall performance [60]. Key differences of both services include channel state information (CSI) availability, directionality and timing of energy arrival, operating frequency, and input power range at the receiver [61], [62]. These requirements directly influence the antenna design [63], e.g., directivity, gain, and polarization, which may differ substantially from existing antenna technologies for RF EH circuits [64]. Moreover, to handle energy density variations over a wide spectrum one can resort to multi-band [65] or, more advanced, tunable [66] RF EH circuits, as shown in Fig. 2.15 (left). Boosting conversion efficiency while providing a broader beamwidth to harvest energy from multiple directions can be achieved with RF EH circuits comprising signal combiners in both RF and direct current domains, as shown in Fig. 2.15 (center). Notably, minimizing energy consumption during precoder optimization is crucial and has been tested through methods such as brute force, sequential testing, and codebook-based strategies [53].

Received power levels significantly vary between dedicated and ambient power transmissions, necessitating rectifier designs capable of operating efficiently across a broad dynamic range. To address this challenge, one can equip the RF EH circuit with multiple rectifiers, as shown in Fig. 2.15 (right), each optimized for a reduced set of input power [67]. Note that such an operation can be achieved with low-complexity distribution networks which automatically route the incoming RF signal to the optimal rectification path without requiring external control circuits [68].

2.2.3 Unmanned Aerial Vehicle-Based Wireless Power Transfer to Remote Energy-Neutral Devices

Many IoT devices operate in remote or harsh environments (e.g., forests, below bridges, underground locations), where EH from ambient sources is not always feasible or sufficient. Replacing or manually recharging batteries is labor-intensive and costly. UAVs can autonomously reach these devices, hover nearby, and wirelessly deliver energy, enabling continuous operation without human intervention. Therefore, energy delivery from a nearby mobile energy source, such as an UAV, offers a promising solution to overcome power limitations in the field [69]–[71].

The transfer from the UAV to the END can be supported by various WPT techniques [72]. In the literature, mainly RF systems (often combined with data transmission) and inductive systems have been investigated. Depending on the END energy requirements, which in turn depend on the related device class (as defined in D2.1), RF WPT may be preferred over inductive power transfer (IPT) or magnetic resonance coupling (MRC) systems. It is assumed that the UAV will often need to hover. This allows the distance between the transmitter and receiver to be reduced, thereby limiting energy losses in the WPT link. Given the power consumption of a hovering UAV, energy transfer should therefore take place as quickly as possible. The power density of RF-based systems is generally lower due to their low efficiency and the limitations on radiated power imposed by regulations such as those from European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). For small ENDs (class 1 devices), RF WPT can be considered a suitable transfer technology. However, when larger amounts of energy need to be transferred in a short time, a coupled WPT system is preferred due to its higher power density.

Recent research has further examined magnetic resonance coupling (MRC) technology implemented on an UAV. [73] investigated the number of required UAV visits based on the size of the energy buffer and charging rate (C-rate), the daily energy consumption of the IoT node, and the power density of the WPT link. The overall energy efficiency for a specific UAV model was analyzed in [74]. Specifically, the UAV's energy consumption for charging the IoT energy buffer and flying to his location compared to the stored energy in the IoT energy buffer. The implementation of a UAV with a proof of concept implementation was studied in [75].

2.2.3.1 MRC Technology for Deployment on UAVs

MRC is a wireless power transfer technique that uses magnetic fields and resonance to transfer energy between two coils over longer distances compared to IPT. Both the transmitter and receiver coils are tuned to the same resonant frequency using capacitors. When both sides resonate at the same frequency, energy transfer becomes more efficient, even if the coils are not perfectly aligned or are spaced farther apart than in standard inductive coupling. The mutual coupling factor is typically below 0.1. Due to this low coupling factor, the self-inductance of each individual coil changes only slightly, resulting in negligible impact on the resonance circuits. MRC still relies on magnetic induction as the underlying physical principle, but resonance enables looser coupling and longer transfer distances without a significant drop in efficiency. The inverter frequency on the transmitter side should remain constant, while the inverter voltage can be adjusted during energy transfer. This allows the efficiency of the entire WPT link to be controlled and optimized, especially under variable load conditions.

On the UAV side, an MRC transmitter is required, consisting of a pre-regulator, inverter, and LC tank. The implementation on the UAV could be realized as illustrated in Figure 2.16. The

Figure 2.16: Render of an autonomous IoT charging system. The UAV battery powers the flight controller and pre-regulator, which drives the half-bridge inverter connected to the transmission coil. The receiver coil captures the magnetic field to charge the IoT energy storage [75].

details of the transmitter side are not further elaborated in this discussion, and the reader is referred to [75].

2.2.3.2 MRC Receiver on the IoT Device Side

This section focuses on the additional components required to make an END or IoT device compatible with the proposed UAV-based approach. This principle is primarily relevant for class-3 devices with the presence of long-term rechargeable energy storage, such as the examples from D2.1. In addition to the application microcontroller and the sensors/actuators specific to the considered application, other components are needed to convert the alternating magnetic fields emitted by the UAV into energy.

The components required for the energy receiver, as shown in Figure 2.17, include an LC tank tuned to the same frequency as the transmitter, a rectifier, and a wake-up and voltage detection circuit that brings the application microcontroller out of sleep or power-down mode via an interrupt pin. A protection circuit is included to disconnect the supply in case of high voltage spikes, while the energy buffer is charged using an efficient switched mode power supply (SMPS). If constant-current charging is required, a current sense circuit can be incorporated. Finally, a bidirectional load switch prevents reverse current from flowing from the energy buffer to the charging circuit.

2.3 Power Management Circuits

This section introduces several power management circuits, such as EH from PV cells, EH from thermal sources and EH from multiple sources. The power management unit (PMU) forms the crucial part of a batteryless IoT design by ensuring regulated and managed power output to the device from an often unstable ambient energy source. Moreover, the energy balance monitoring and voltage limiting techniques for ENDs are also discussed.

Figure 2.17: Schematic representation of the MRC WPT receiver. GPIO1, GPIO2, and GPIO3 correspond to the wake-up input, protection-enable output, and buck-enable output, respectively. ADC1 and ADC2 are used to measure the input voltage and output current. The microcontroller unit (MCU) and IoT-specific components, such as sensors or actuators, are not shown, as these depend on the specific use case [75].

2.3.1 Energy-Neutral Device Energy Harvesting from a Photovoltaic Cell

Using PV cells to harvest energy shows a promising way to empower ENDS, which has been discussed in Section 2.1.1.

The simplest way to harvest power from a PV cell is to connect the panel to a capacitor with a diode. The diode prevents current flow from the capacitor to the panel when the light is low. Even with a large panel, the output voltage will be low in low-light situations. A boost converter would be necessary to raise the voltage to a usable level. With a large panel, the maximum output voltage will be high, and either the storage must be able to handle the voltage or a converter is needed to lower the voltage to the storage level. Another way to harvest power from a solar panel is to use a harvester circuit that combines maximum power point tracking (MPPT) with the boost converter. MPPT can be implemented for example by measuring the open circuit voltage periodically and adjusting the harvester input voltage to a fraction of this, or by making small changes to the input voltage and measuring the change in the current.

In situations when only a low level of light is available, the output voltage from a low-power solar panel can be less than 1 V. The harvester circuit must be able to operate in such situations. On the other hand, the maximum input voltage of the harvester sets an upper limit on the solar panel output voltage. The harvester circuit should also implement some form of MPPT. Voltage in the energy storage varies and can be over the voltage limits of the system components. Some form of voltage regulator is needed. A switching regulator has lower losses than a linear regulator, but requires an external inductor and may cause noise in other components. Integrating the regulator into the harvester simplifies the system. In addition, a primary battery can be used as a backup power source to keep the device operational for extended low periods of insufficient light. The harvester should be able to switch between harvested power and the backup automatically.

As an example, the power management circuit of an END, Li2BC [76], is discussed in the following paragraphs.

2.3.1.1 Energy Harvester Circuit

Energy harvester chosen for analysis in this section is Analog Devices ADP5091 [77], which is a part of the aforementioned Li2BC device. It collects energy from a PV cell using maximum power point tracking and uses the energy to charge the energy storage capacitors. It can also

Figure 2.18: ADP5091 functional block diagram [77].

use a backup battery to provide power in case the storage voltage drops to an insufficient level.

The operation of the harvester depends on the energy storage voltage V_{BAT} . To prevent energy storage overvoltage, the charging is terminated when V_{BAT} reaches the voltage V_{BAT_TERM} . The storage capacitors are disconnected when V_{BAT} is below the stop discharge voltage V_{SETSD} . The supercapacitors are not damaged by undervoltage but at this storage voltage level the regulated output drops below the microcontroller requirement. Disconnecting the capacitors minimizes the leakage.

The set backup voltage V_{SETBK} is the storage voltage level that determines if the backup battery is used to power the device. The set power good V_{SETPG} sets the voltage threshold to enable the microcontroller power. The V_{SETBK} and V_{SETPG} voltages have hysteresis. The actual threshold changes depending on if the storage voltage V_{BAT} is rising (\uparrow) or falling (\downarrow).

Voltage thresholds are collected in table 2.4. The thresholds have some variance that depends on the harvester’s internal voltage reference. The thresholds are set with external resistors.

The harvester has a low-light indicator that can be used to indicate to the microcontroller when sufficient light for EH is not available. The harvester boost converter can also be disabled to reduce noise, for example in the case of sensitive measurements.

2.3.1.2 Energy Storage

An END must have sufficient energy storage to be able to run in low-light situations, when the PV cells do not produce energy. The amount of energy storage and power consumption sets the device run time without external energy. Supercapacitors have significant internal leakage, which must be taken into account when implementing energy storage.

The total stored charge in the capacitors is

$$Q = nCV_{\Delta}, \tag{2.4}$$

Table 2.4: Controller voltage thresholds.

Threshold	Reference	Typical/V	Range/V
$V_{\text{BAT_TERM}}$	$V_{\text{BAT}} \uparrow$	5.04	4.77–5.31
V_{SETSD}	$V_{\text{BAT}} \downarrow$	2.63	2.48–2.77
V_{SETBK}	$V_{\text{BAT}} \uparrow$	2.98	2.81–3.14
V_{SETBK}	$V_{\text{BAT}} \downarrow$	3.12	2.94–3.28
V_{SETPG}	$V_{\text{BAT}} \uparrow$	3.04	2.87–3.20
V_{SETPG}	$V_{\text{BAT}} \downarrow$	2.78	2.62–2.93

where n is the number of capacitors, C is the capacitance of a single capacitor, and V_{Δ} is the voltage over the capacitors. The current consumption I of on END has three main parts: The working current I_{work} , including the microcontroller, sensors, and communication, losses in the system I_{loss} , and internal leakage of the capacitors I_{leak} .

The capacitor discharge time t is related to the charge with

$$Q = tI. \quad (2.5)$$

Thus, when powered solely by the energy storage, the run time is then

$$t_{\text{run}} = \frac{Q}{I} = \frac{nCV_{\Delta}}{I_{\text{work}} + I_{\text{loss}} + I_{\text{leak}}} \quad (2.6)$$

Supercapacitors with capacitance $C = 0.1 \text{ F}$ from Kemet FG series [78] were chosen for energy storage. 5V supercapacitors from the series have voltage-holding characteristic of 4.2V, or voltage drop $V_{\Delta} = 0.8 \text{ V}$ over $t_{\text{test}} = 24 \text{ h}$. Based on that, the internal leakage current I_l can be estimated to be

$$I_{\text{leak}} = \frac{CV_{\Delta}}{t_{\text{test}}} = 0.9 \mu\text{A}. \quad (2.7)$$

The fully charged voltage of the supercapacitors is 5.0V. The microcontroller input and output voltage is equal to the supercapacitor voltage minus the LDO voltage drop (0.3V). In order to keep the input-output voltage compatible with external digital components, it should be at least 2.5V. Therefore, the lowest working voltage of the supercapacitors is 3.0V, and then $V_{\Delta} = 2.0 \text{ V}$.

On tests done with NUCLEO-L55ZEQ demo board, the working current I_{work} was estimated to be $4 \mu\text{A}$. In addition, $I_{\text{loss}} = 1 \mu\text{A}$ is estimated to be wasted on various component losses. Based on these numbers, the run time with different numbers of capacitors can be estimated using Equation (2.6).

Table 2.5 shows the estimated run times. It can be noted that the run time does not increase linearly with the number of capacitors. As the number of capacitors is increased, the fraction of the work current from each capacitor diminishes. With these assumptions about the currents, with more than 5 capacitors the self discharge current is greater than actual work current per each capacitor, and additional capacitors do not significantly increase the run time.

Table 2.5: Estimated runtime in hours with different number of supercapacitors.

Capacitors	1	2	3	4	5	6
t/h	9.4	16.3	21.6	25.8	29.2	32.0

2.3.2 Power Management Circuits for Thermal Energy Harvesting

Similarly to solar energy harvesters, thermal generators require dedicated circuit techniques to operate efficiently. The low voltages and relatively high source impedance of TEGs make impedance matching and cold-start capability essential design considerations. Several power management integrated circuits (PMICs) have been developed specifically to address these challenges, as illustrated by the following examples.

- **Analog Devices LTC3108** [79], [80]– This ultra-low voltage step-up converter supports input voltages as low as 20 mV through the use of an external step-up transformer, enabling the operation of a TEG with temperature differences as small as 1 °C. The transformer provides impedance transformation, allowing the device to draw power efficiently from high-impedance sources. The LTC3108 is designed to present an effective input resistance in the range of 2–10 Ω , depending on the transformer turn ratio and the input voltage. As the input voltage decreases, the converter’s input resistance increases, which enables approximate impedance matching with the internal resistance of typical TEGs, thereby improving energy transfer efficiency under varying thermal conditions.
- **E-peas AEM20940** [81], [82] – This PMIC supports input voltages as low as 50 mV, with a cold-start capability from 50–380 mV, depending on the available input power. It integrates an adaptive MPPT algorithm that periodically samples the input voltage to dynamically match the source impedance. Unlike transformer-based solutions, the AEM20940 employs a fully integrated boost converter, which simplifies system integration and reduces overall size. The device features dual-regulated outputs and directly supports energy storage in supercapacitors or rechargeable batteries and includes autonomous load management based on state of charge (SoC).

2.3.3 Multisource Power Management Units

Over the last decades, the state-of-the-art of PMU has substantially improved, both in academic and industrial research. There are numerous off-the-shelf PMUs available in the market, specifically tailored to various EH applications and use cases. However, a majority of the development on PMUs has been focused on a single source PMU that can harness energy from one source at a time. The nature of the deployment environment often determines the choice of the energy source of an ambient-powered device. In many situations, there can be more than one source available. However, the lack of PMUs that can accommodate more than one source at a time limits the exploitation of multiple sources for EH. A multisource PMU must simultaneously harvest energy from multiple sources without causing reverse energy flow between the sources and charge a storage element. However, this is not a trivial task, mainly due to the wide range of electrical characteristics possessed by different energy harvesters (Section 2.1). Therefore, harvesting energy from these varieties of energy sources implies the front end of the PMU should be capable of seamlessly tuning its electrical characteristics. Since the energy available to cold-

Figure 2.19: Different energy combining topologies (a) diodes used to select the strongest source (b) capacitor or the (c) of a switching regulator shared and multiplexed between multiple sources.

start a PMU is typically very limited, adding such luxuries can impair its overall performance if not carefully managed.

A naive approach to multisource harvesting is to use an energy-OR circuit to add the sources together (Fig. 2.19). The energy OR-ing is the most basic and easy-to-use circuit in which diodes or MOSFETs provide isolation between the input sources [83]–[85]. However, such circuits provide the least efficiency since only the highest energy source is utilised at any time due to the diode/FET’s OR-ing property. A second approach is to use time-multiplexing circuits at the front end, which provides access to the source in a specific window. Time multiplexing circuits can be implemented using capacitors with voltage thresholds to transfer and combine energy from multiple sources [86]–[88]. These circuits overcome the limitation of energy OR-ing circuits by sequentially transferring energy from one source to the storage buffer based on voltage thresholds. Though they have superior performance over OR-ing circuits, they fail to support simultaneous EH. Additionally, their reliance on capacitors for energy transfer can impact the efficiency when using supercapacitors or capacitors as the main storage buffer due to the energy lost in energy transfer between capacitors. Another set of multisource front-ends uses the time multiplexing concept, but with a shared inductor between sources to combine energy [89]–[91]. The sources are sequentially connected to the inductor of a boost converter to enable energy transfer.

On the industrial side, PMUs for EH have matured significantly over the past decade. Today, there exists a wide variety of PMUs, each optimised for different sources, power levels, and application requirements. Despite this progress, most commercially available EH ICs still manage only one source at a time. While many support different input types (e.g., solar cells, piezoelectric harvesters, or thermoelectric generators), they typically allow only a single source to be connected in a given configuration. For instance, PMU such as AKM AP4413, Texas Instruments BQ25570, or Analog Devices ADP5090 are optimized for single-source input and are highly efficient for PV or TEG operation. Nexperia’s NEH71×0 chips bring novelty to the market with their inductor-less architecture, which reduces footprint and bill of materials (BoM) cost. Though fabless companies such as e-peas and Trameto have made attempts at multi-source PMUs, the field of multisource PMU itself remains in its early stages and is yet to reach

maturity. For instance, the e-peas AEM13920¹ supports dual-source EH inputs, while Tramoto's OptiJoule TR-J301² claims to accommodate up to four inputs with an exceptionally low cold-start voltage. However, these are still in their early design phase and are yet to be available in the market.

2.3.3.1 Energy Combiners

An energy combiner (EC) forms an essential part of the multisource PMU front-end. The primary function of an EC is to ensure the maximum energy is extracted from multiple sources simultaneously and the extracted energy is transferred to a storage element. Additionally, the latest ECs may incorporate extra features into it, such as harvest rate sensing and MPPT [92]. EC may be used to harvest and combine energy from the transducers directly, in which case it will incorporate a DC-DC converter as well. Otherwise, a separate off-chip DC-DC converter may be used for each energy source, with the EC then accumulating energy from each of these converters. The latter is useful when COTS DC-DC converters are preferred, as the nature of the energy source may vary from design to design, and the design needs to be modular and flexible.

A high-level architecture of an EC is shown in Fig. 2.20. The architecture fundamentally relies on capacitor-to-capacitor energy transfer. Further, the EC does not incorporate DC-DC converters at the harvester side. Therefore, the inputs to the EC are assumed to be from respective DC-DC converters. Thus, any off-the-shelf PMUs available in the market can be used, making the design of EC portable and harvester agnostic. Currently, EC shows only two sources, but the architecture can be extended to any number of PMUs. The energy generated by each PMU is stored in temporary buffers before they are transferred to the main buffer. These temporary buffers are relatively small (μF). In a conventional method, where energy is transferred between two capacitors of the same size, at least half of the energy is wasted. However, we mitigate this issue by using a current-controlled switching regulator. The switching regulator is configured to be in buck-boost mode, allowing the source to be charged to any voltage level irrespective of the output of the PMU. We further use two temporary buffers per source to ensure that the energy from the source is always harvested. Therefore, unlike time multiplexing circuits, where the source is harvested sequentially and left dormant between charge transfers, the proposed architecture ensures maximum utilization of the energy source. Two threshold voltage levels, V_H and V_L , decide the transfer of energy from the temporary buffer to the main buffer or from the PMU to the temporary buffer. Comparator circuits with hysteresis monitor the voltage of the capacitors and generate triggers when the voltage goes above V_H or below V_L . A control unit responds to this trigger and manages the charging and discharging of the capacitors.

2.3.4 Energy Balance Monitoring

Reliable operation of ENDS requires an accurate tracking of the available energy to ensure that consumption remains within the limits of harvested and stored power. By quantifying the energy present in storage buffers (such as supercapacitors or rechargeable batteries), the system can dynamically adapt its behavior through informed task scheduling, load modulation, or deferral

¹AEM13920

²OptiJoule

Figure 2.20: A high-level architecture of the energy combiner circuit. Eight comparators, two per capacitor, are used to monitor the charge-discharge of temporary buffers. The comparator signals are monitored by the control unit, which steers the energy transfer from the temporary buffer to the main buffer C_{STORE} .

of non-critical processes. Several techniques and ICs are available to support such energy-aware operation.

2.3.4.1 Voltage-based Fuel Gauges

In Supercapacitor based ENDS When supercapacitors are used as the only energy storage element, the remaining available energy can be estimated directly from the supercap terminal voltage, assuming stable capacitance and negligible leakage. Monitoring this voltage allows for a straightforward and energy-efficient estimation of the stored energy using low-power analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) or integrated voltage supervisors.

The available energy E in the supercapacitor can be computed as:

$$E = \frac{1}{2}CV^2 \tag{2.8}$$

where E is the stored energy in joules, C is the capacitance in farads, and V is the measured terminal voltage. From this, SoC can be estimated relative to the maximum voltage V_{max} as:

$$SoC = \left(\frac{V}{V_{max}}\right)^2 \tag{2.9}$$

Here, SoC represents the ratio of the current stored energy to the maximum possible energy, with V_{max} being the fully charged voltage of the supercapacitor.

In Battery based ENDS Unlike supercapacitors, batteries exhibit voltage–SoC characteristics that are often described as nonlinear and depend on multiple factors such as chemistry, temperature, aging, and load conditions, whereas supercapacitors show a simpler dependence on charge.

In lithium-based batteries (e.g., Li-ion, LiPo), open circuit voltage (OCV) generally increases monotonically with SoC, but the relationship is far from linear. For example, a small voltage drop near the end of discharge can correspond to a substantial decrease in SoC, complicating accurate voltage-based estimation without proper compensation. Furthermore, during charging or discharging, the terminal voltage is affected by the internal resistance and transient current of the battery, causing deviations from the true OCV.

SoC can be derived by measuring the battery voltage and comparing it with a (static) model of the battery behavior. An example of such an approach is implemented in devices like the Analog Devices MAX17048 [93], which requires an empirically acquired battery model to be programmed into the device. At its core, this method uses OCV to SoC lookup tables tailored to the specific chemistry and design of the battery. These lookup tables require that the battery rests sufficiently long to reach equilibrium, allowing the terminal voltage to approximate the true OCV before measurement.

To further enhance the SoC accuracy during active operation, the battery voltage can be sampled after a defined rest period following charging or discharging events. This relaxation period helps to better approximate OCV and thereby improves SoC accuracy under dynamic conditions.

2.3.4.2 Battery: Coulomb Counting

Coulomb counting involves continuously measuring and integrating the current entering and exiting the energy storage device over time. Through the integration of the net charge flow, it is possible to determine the SoC of the battery with high precision [94]. This methodology relies on accurate current measuring instruments, such as a shunt or Hall-effect sensors, and precise time measurement to enable accurate integration of the current. In practice, however, coulomb counting is affected by sensor offset, drift, noise, and other practical measurement limitations [95], which, if left uncorrected, can cause a gradual divergence in the accuracy of SoC estimation. To mitigate these errors, Coulomb counting is often combined with periodic voltage-based corrections or model-based filtering techniques to improve accuracy. For example, the Analog Devices MAX17260 [96] implements the proprietary ModelGauge m5 EZ algorithm which combines coulomb counting with OCV estimation and temperature compensation to achieve improved SoC accuracy. The algorithm eliminates the need for prior battery characterization and adapts to battery aging and variations in discharge rate.

2.3.5 Voltage Limiting Techniques for Energy-Neutral Devices

In ENDS, where energy is harvested from ambient sources such as RF signals, PV cells, TEGs, piezoelectric harvesters or others, voltage limiting circuits are indispensable for ensuring safe and efficient operation of downstream electronics. These circuits are responsible for clamping the input or output voltage of the EH front-end to a safe level, thereby preventing overvoltage-induced degradation or destruction of sensitive integrated components. As technology nodes scale down, the maximum tolerable voltage drops accordingly, making robust voltage limiting essential for reliable operation [21], [25].

The design of voltage limiters for ambient EH applications is particularly challenging due to stringent power constraints and the need for ultra-low leakage. These circuits must exhibit leakage currents in the picoampere range to avoid draining the limited harvested energy. Furthermore,

Figure 2.21: Schematic of the DC voltage limiter with PTAT compensation [25].

they must operate reliably across a wide range of input power levels and environmental conditions, including temperature variations and fluctuating light or vibration levels in the case of PV and piezoelectric sources.

A common approach involves shunt-based limiters using metal-oxide semiconductor (MOS) transistors biased in the subthreshold region. These devices act as voltage-controlled resistive paths that become conductive only when the input voltage exceeds a defined threshold. More advanced techniques include dynamic threshold scaling, gated body biasing, and auxiliary charge pump activation, which allow the limiter to respond intelligently to varying input conditions [25], [97].

DC Voltage Limiting DC voltage limiters are typically placed at the output of the EH front-end to protect the core circuitry from excessive supply voltages. In the implementation by Zöscher et al. [25], illustrated in Fig. 2.21, a proportional to absolute temperature (PTAT)-compensated DC limiter is used to maintain a stable clipping voltage across temperature variations. The PTAT voltage is generated by a stack of diode-connected N-channel metal-oxide semiconductor (NMOS) transistors operating in the subthreshold region. The limiter includes a cascade of four PTAT unit cells and a shunt transistor controlled by a temperature-compensated bias voltage. This ensures that the output voltage remains below the technology limit of 1.2 V even under rapid power surges [25].

The dynamic behavior of the DC limiter is illustrated in Figure 2.22, which shows the transient response of the output voltage V_{DC} during startup and under modulated RF excitation. The measurements were performed at two different available power levels: a high-power condition of 24 dBm and a low-power threshold condition $P_{av,min}$. The limiter successfully clamps the output voltage below 1.2 V in both cases, demonstrating its effectiveness in protecting the core circuitry during rapid power transitions and startup events.

RF Voltage Limiting For RF inputs, voltage limiting must occur at the front-end interface to prevent breakdown of the rectifier or charge pump transistors. Zöscher et al. [21] proposed two RF limiter designs for differential ultra-high frequency (UHF) RFID front-ends in 40 nm CMOS. The first design, shown in Figure 2.23, uses NMOS transistors as ground-referred active loads. The gate control voltage $V_{BN,Lim}$ is generated by a two-stage auxiliary charge pump. At low input amplitudes, the limiter remains inactive, preserving sensitivity. As V_{in} increases, the auxiliary pump activates, raising $V_{BN,Lim}$ and turning on the NMOS load transistors to shunt excess energy.

Figure 2.22: Transient measurement results of the output voltage V_{DC} during startup and under modulated carrier waveforms at $P_{av} = 24 \text{ dBm}$ and $P_{av,min}$ [25].

Figure 2.23: Schematic of the RF voltage limiter using ground-referred NMOS devices [21].

Figure 2.24: Schematic of the RF voltage limiter with complementary NMOS and PMOS active load devices [21].

The second design, shown in Fig. 2.24, employs a fully complementary topology with NMOS and P-channel metal-oxide semiconductor (PMOS) transistors directly connected to the RF pads. This configuration reduces the overall transistor dimensions by approximately 25% compared to the NMOS-only design. It requires an isolated p-well, available in triple-well CMOS processes, to generate the negative bias voltage $V_{BP, Lim}$. Additional ground-referenced transistors are used to balance the DC signal level at the RF nodes and mitigate electrostatic discharge (ESD) risks.

Post-layout simulations confirm that both limiter designs become active at approximately 0.5 V and effectively clamp V_{in} to below 1.1 V at an available power of 20 dBm. The added input capacitance C_p from the limiter circuits is minimal, contributing less than 10% to the total

front-end capacitance. This ensures that the bandwidth and impedance matching characteristics of the front-end remain largely unaffected.

Generalization to Ambient IoT Sources While the above designs are tailored for RF inputs, similar voltage limiting principles apply to other ambient energy sources. For example, PV cells under direct sunlight can generate open-circuit voltages exceeding 2V, which often must be clamped before reaching sensitive analog or digital blocks. In such cases, voltage limiters are often integrated with MPPT circuits or low-dropout voltage regulators (LDOs) that include overvoltage protection stages. For TEGs and piezoelectric harvesters, which can produce voltage spikes due to thermal or mechanical transients, fast-acting limiter circuits with low input capacitance are essential to prevent latch-up or gate oxide breakdown.

Complementary Techniques In addition to dedicated limiter circuits, several complementary techniques are employed in modern energy-neutral systems, to use the available energy more effectively:

- **Dynamic Voltage Scaling:** Adjusts the supply voltage based on workload (for example based on a DC-DC converter), reducing energy consumption during idle periods and mitigating overvoltage risks.
- **Multi-Threshold CMOS:** Combines high- V_{TH} transistors for leakage reduction with low- V_{TH} devices for performance-critical paths.
- **Adaptive Body Biasing:** Dynamically tunes the threshold voltage of transistors to optimize performance and reduce susceptibility to overvoltage.

Together, these techniques form a comprehensive strategy for voltage regulation in ultra-low power systems. Their integration into EH front-ends ensures safe operation, ensure good efficiency, and supports scaling toward next-generation energy-autonomous IoT devices.

2.4 Summary

Chapter 2 reviews ambient energy sources such as light, heat, vibration, and RF signals, and introduces dedicated WPT for cases where ambient supply is insufficient. For each source, we summarize conversion front ends, rectifiers, and charge pump options, along with key link-budget considerations. The chapter then presents multisource power management, which integrates multiple harvesters, handles cold start, prioritizes inputs, and protects storage and loads through voltage limiting and current control. It further defines the interfaces between harvesters, storage, and loads, emphasizing low quiescent consumption and predictable transient behavior. Finally, the chapter concludes with measurement guidelines and selection criteria that directly inform the device platforms and communication strategies discussed in subsequent chapters.

Chapter 3

Low-power IoT Devices, Backscatter Devices, and Wake-up Radio Design

This chapter examines END platforms for low-power IoT, backscatter device (BD), and wake-up radio designs, which succeeds the discussion of the proposed END concept in the deliverable D2.1. It links platform selection, sensing profiles, and compute needs to measured energy budgets and realistic duty cycles. We summarize criteria for microcontrollers, memory, clocks, and peripherals with deterministic wake and sleep behavior, together with firmware hooks for energy-aware scheduling. For backscatter, we outline reader and tag building blocks, describe impedance modulation and radar cross section, and frame range, throughput, and inventory latency as functions of reader density and regulations. For wake-up radios, we present front ends, correlators, and trigger logic that reduce idle listening while bounding false alarm probability and response time, with simple coupling to the main radio.

3.1 Low-power Internet of Things Device Prototypes

In this section, two low-power IoT prototypes are introduced, including the Digital Enhanced Cordless Telecommunications (DECT)-2020 device and cellular IoT device.

3.1.1 DECT-2020 Device

3.1.1.1 DECT-2020 NR Overview

DECT-2020 NR [98] is a noncellular 5G standard developed by ETSI that supports ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC) and massive machine-typed communication (mMTC) in IoT applications.

Using DECT-2020, devices can transmit device-to-device or broadcast to all devices in range. In a multi-device network, a single DECT-2020 device acts as a base station, allocating radio resources to other devices in the network. The base station acts as a gateway to other networks. DECT-2020 also supports the mesh network topology, where the base stations of different networks communicate with each other.

DECT-2020 operates on a dedicated licence-exempt frequency band around 1.9 GHz, with actual frequencies depending on the market. It uses frequency division for network multiplexing and

Figure 3.1: Left: Aalto DM51 DECT-2020 Module. Right: Aalto DM51 as Raspberry Pi add-on board.

time division for device access multiplexing. DECT-2020 standard specifies the transmit power levels from -40 dBm to 32 dBm to optimise range, interference, and power consumption.

3.1.1.2 Aalto DM51

DM51 (DECT Module with nRF9151) shown in Figure 3.1, is a 65 mm by 50 mm module built around the Nordic Semiconductor nRF9151 [99] system-in-package (SiP). The module includes the nRF9151 SiP, a ceramic wideband antenna, and a Nordic Semiconductor nPM1300 [100] PMIC. There is also a provision for the use of an external antenna.

The module can operate stand-alone, for example as a sensor node, or as an add-on module connected to a host computer such as Raspberry Pi. In standalone operation, the module is powered by a lithium polymer (LiPo) battery or via the USB port. The host provides power when the module is used as an add-on.

The nRF9151 SiP integrates ARM Cortex-M33 processor, 1 MB flash read-only memory (ROM), 256 kB random-access memory (RAM), a multi-protocol modem (Long Term Evolution (LTE), DECT, global navigation satellite system (GNSS)), and various input/output (IO) interfaces. The universal serial bus (USB) port is used for module software updates and as a serial port. Seven SiP IO lines are routed to an expansion connector in the module, and their functionality can be adjusted with software. The nPM1300 PMIC handles the LiPo battery charging and power supplies for the rest of the module.

Figure 3.2 shows the nRF9151 SiP power consumption when transmitting a DECT broadcast message with 0 dBm transmit power and 3.0 V supply voltage. The mean power consumption during a transmission is 234 mW, and approximately 100 mW when idle between transmissions.

As of this time, low power operation of the module is not yet characterized. However, manufacturer specifications [100] can be used for estimations. In the nRF9151 SiP, the modem is the highest consuming component using 34 mA from 3.7 V supply when idle, and more when transmitting. The CPU core consumes 2.1 mA running a stress test application, and the CPU consumption is down to $2 \mu\text{A}$ in a sleep mode. This indicates that for low power operation the modem should be turned off most of the time.

Figure 3.2: nRF9151 SiP current consumption when transmitting a DECT message.

3.1.2 Cellular Internet of Things Device

Cellular IoT devices often transmit and receive relatively small amounts of user data. For example, a smart meter unit will typically transmit a few hundred bytes of information per day. Between transmissions, these devices may enter a so-called power saving mode (PSM), where the terminal remains registered with the network but stops listening entirely for typically several hours. Most devices are configured to go to sleep mode for extended periods and wake up periodically, typically every few minutes, to listen for paging messages. For these devices, manufacturers still target battery lifetimes of 10-15 years. Finally, there are devices that need to be reachable at short notice, for example, to receive voice calls. These will negotiate sleep periods of no more than a few seconds with the network.

Considering the emerging NR-based cellular IoT devices, the lowest power NR eRedCap devices like smart meters will likely be powered from a battery, specifically an A-size lithium thionyl chloride (LTC) battery which has exceptional voltage stability across a wide temperature range, a near-flat discharge profile, as well as low self-discharge, and can provide a storage capacity of about 3.6 Ah at 3.65 V (equivalent to 47 kJ of energy). To last 15 years, the device must consume less than 9 Joule per day or below 100 μ W averaged in time.

For cellular battery-based A-IoT devices, an ambitious target will be to power a device from a much smaller battery, e.g., a CR2032 coin battery. However, overall energy storage will be considerably lower (about 2.4 kJ considering 225 mAh capacity at 3 V). The lithium manganese oxide chemistry used provides a lower voltage, especially at low temperature, and lower peak currents.

This section will first describe the impact of the various memory/storage options on the device design. Then, considering this memory impact and the different operational modes, we identify Low Power Management (LPM) strategies for power saving and we identify potential relaxations at receiver design.

3.1.2.1 Memory/Storage Options

Any cellular IoT device will have to store code for controlling the device hardware and run the cellular protocol stack. It will also store and process data, for example, user TCP/IP packets, voice samples, or encoded IQ samples.

Table 3.1: Memory options comparison

Parameter	External NOR	External DRAM	Internal SRAM	Unit
Data retention	Non-volatile	Volatile	Volatile	–
Interface	QSPI, DDR	X8 SPI, DDR	32-bit, internal	–
Cost (excl. package)	3	2	12	¢/MB
Clock speed	100	250	500	MHz
Write speed	2	500	2,000	MB/s
Read speed	100	500	2,000	MB/s
Write energy	7,000	60	3	$\mu\text{J MB}^{-1}$
Read energy	200	60	3	$\mu\text{J MB}^{-1}$
Retention power	0	5	200	$\mu\text{W MB}^{-1}$

In a typical architecture, there are three principal choices for storing code and data. Firstly, there is flash memory (NOR or NAND flash), which is non-volatile and can store information for years without consuming power. However, access speed is low (especially for write) and the number of erase/program operations is typically limited to 100k cycles over the product lifetime. Secondly, dynamic random-access memory (DRAM) stores bits using cells made up of a single transistor and a single capacitor. As a result, these memories are compact and cost-effective. However, because of device leakage, period self-refresh is required to maintain the stored information. Finally, SRAM may be used to store information using flip-flops. Most implementations use six transistors per bitcell. While no refresh mechanism is needed, the flip-flops still exhibit some gate leakage, especially in smaller silicon process geometries.

SRAM is nearly always integrated within the SoC which maximizes access speed and minimizes active power consumption. By contrast, we find flash and DRAM devices typically implemented outside the SoC but often integrated within the same package. This compromise allows each component to use the most suitable and cost-effective silicon process technology.

Table 3.1 below compares the three storage options in terms of access speed and power consumption. The figures are based on low-cost but state-of-the-art devices used in today's cellular IoT products. The transfer energy figures include power required to drive the physical interfaces between the SoC and external memory chips.

The table exposes drastic differences in cost, access speed and energy as well as data retention power. The following section will discuss different strategies to use these storage media for different sleep durations.

3.1.2.2 LPM Strategies

Starting from PSM, it is clear that all code and data retention should use non-volatile flash memory. For example, context information established during cell attachment must be stored together with RF configurations such as channel frequency and bandwidth, so that at the next wake up the device can quickly reconnect, and resume operation as needed.

For long sleep duration (minutes), it is still preferable to power down the entire SoC and store

all code and context data in flash memory. The downside of this approach is that the reboot process will take longer due to slow access to the flash. Keeping the amount of code and data loaded to a minimum is key for minimizing battery consumption.

For shorter sleep durations (seconds), retaining all code and context data in DRAM becomes more attractive. While leakage is non-zero, it is still low, and the energy required to re-boot the system is much smaller compared to re-booting from flash memory.

Only for the shortest idle periods (milliseconds), it is beneficial to retain information in SoC-internal static random-access memory (SRAM) in order to avoid overheads for re-configuring the chip for the next active slots.

In future work, we will develop detailed models to analyze the exact trade-offs involved. We will also outline the amount of code that is required for certain operations. For example, we will demonstrate that providing dedicated low complexity wake up signals (like the NR LP-SS and LP-WUS signals currently being defined in 3GPP Release 19) lower both the amount of code required as well as the modem processing time which reduces overall power consumption.

Our goal is to provide a power model based on 5G NR technology that can provide an A-size battery lifetime of 15+ years and outline several enhancements fit for A-IoT technology and devices that make it possible to further lower power consumption to eventually eliminate batteries altogether.

3.1.2.3 LPM Receiver

Depending on the mode that the device has to operate, the requirements for the various circuitry can be relaxed and operation may be acceptable at lower currents. We can generally consider, for example, three modes of cellular IoT device operation: 1) Mode-1: Active duplex traffic, requiring Tx and Rx blocks fully operational with high performance; 2) Mode-2: Active traffic reception and transmission at low power or inactive, requiring only Rx operational at optimum performance; 3) Mode-3: Paging monitoring, requiring Rx operational at low performance.

The relaxed requirements due to absence of TX blocker and lower modulation complexity (including, e.g., relaxed in-band and out-of-band phase noise, RF linearity, ADC signal-to-noise ratio (SNR)) can be exploited to save power at the device. Some of the parameters that can be adjusted for maintaining the bare minimum performance and reducing power consumption when in low performance mode are:

- Linearity of the receive chain.
- Transistor current in the voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO) of the local oscillator, frequency dividers, and clock buffers.
- Bit Resolution and/or Sample Rate of the ADC.
- Transistor current in the oscillator of the clock generator for the ADC.
- Number of active filtering stages in the baseband receive chain.
- Load regulation of power supply modules.

Table 3.2 indicates which relaxations are possible depending on the device operating mode.

Table 3.2: Potential relaxations per device operating mode

Device operating mode	Distinct feature	Reduce Linearity	Reduce Oscillator Current/LO buffering	Reduce ADC sample rate/resolution	Reduce ADC clock generator current	Bypass Active Filter
Mode-1	Tx+Rx fully operational	No	No	No	No	No
Mode-2	Rx fully operational, Tx inactive or at low power	Partially	Partially	No	No	Yes
Mode-3	Rx only & operational at low performance	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

In a next deliverable, we will analyze and quantify the impact of the various parameters to understand the benefits of adjustable circuitry operation and where one can exploit similarly relaxed requirements to save power at ENDs devices.

3.2 Backscattering Type of Devices

Backscatter communication (BC) enables ultra-low-power wireless connectivity by reflecting dedicated or ambient RF signals, eliminating the need for active transmission. Recent advances integrate analog and digital modulation, increase energy harvesting efficiency, and implement hybrid visible light communication (VLC)-RF architectures. These developments pave the way for scalable, energy-autonomous A-IoT systems operating in environments with minimal power budgets.

3.2.1 Radio Frequency Identification Technology for Backscattering-Type Energy-Neutral Devices

Passive RFID systems are a cornerstone of ultra-low-power wireless communication, particularly suited for ENDs in A-IoT environments. These systems operate by reflecting incident electromagnetic waves, enabling both data transmission and EH without active RF components [22], [101].

A typical passive RFID setup consists of a reader and a tag. The reader emits an RF signal, which is received by the tag's antenna. The tag modulates its input impedance to encode data onto the backscattered signal. This impedance modulation results in distinct states, which are detected by the reader. The tag's chip switches between two impedance states, resulting in encoding binary information [102].

Figure 3.3 shows a representative RFID front-end architecture developed in 40 nm CMOS technology. It includes a differential RF-DC converter, voltage limiter, and load modulator. Zöscher et al. have demonstrated that such designs can achieve cold-start operation at input powers below -15 dbm, making them ideal for ambient-powered ENDs [21], [24], [25].

The architecture comprises several key blocks that enable backscatter communication:

Figure 3.3: Differential UHF RFID front-end architecture in 40 nm CMOS technology [25].

Receiving and Demodulating the Incoming Signal: The UHF antenna receives the incoming modulated signal at ports RF_1 and RF_2 . Electrostatic discharge protection is provided by ESD diodes. The signal is routed to the demodulator, which follows an envelope detector architecture to convert the received modulated signal into a digital data out bitstream.

Backscattering via RF Modulator: A digital data in signal is fed into the modulator. The modulator dynamically alters its impedance in response to the incoming carrier wave. This impedance variation (shorting the RF front-end) causes a portion of the incident wave to be reflected, encoding the data in signal onto the backscattered wave.

Recent advances in backscatter communication have extended the capabilities of RFID-based systems. Techniques such as harmonic backscattering, intermodulation, and ambient backscatter enable operation over longer distances and in complex environments [101], [103]. These methods exploit nonlinear components or ambient RF sources (e.g., Wi-Fi, bluetooth) to eliminate the need for dedicated readers for energy supply, enabling pervasive deployment of A-IoT devices.

Ambient backscatter is particularly promising. Tags can reflect existing RF signals from infrastructure such as Wi-Fi access points or cell towers, drastically reducing the deployment cost and energy requirements.

The analog front-end plays a critical role in enabling efficient EH and modulation. State-of-the-art designs incorporate threshold voltage compensation, adaptive frequency selection, and differential architectures to improve conversion efficiency and robustness against process variations [21], [24]. These innovations are essential for reliable operation in low-field environments typical of ambient IoT deployments.

Backscattering-type ENDs are particularly suited for applications requiring ultra-low power and long-term autonomy. These include smart infrastructure monitoring, wearable health sensors, asset tracking in supply chains, and environmental sensing. The passive nature of backscatter communication allows for scalable deployments, where a single reader or ambient RF source can support hundreds of tags simultaneously using multiple access schemes such as time division-multiple access (TDMA), frequency division multiple access (FDMA), or compressive sensing-based decoding [103].

In summary, backscatter communication is a foundational technology for energy-neutral wireless

Figure 3.4: BD: (a) System model of LiBD, (b) schematic of LiBD.

systems. Mostly used in the field of RFID, it is now a promising communication technology to enable A-IoT devices. Its passive nature, scalability, and compatibility with ambient RF sources make it a key enabler for the future of sustainable and ubiquitous IoT deployments. The integration of advanced analog front-ends, efficient modulation schemes, and ambient EH techniques continues to push the boundaries of what is possible with backscattering-type ENDS.

3.2.2 Detailed Information on Backscattering-Type Energy-Neutral Devices

3.2.2.1 UP-END, BD with VLC Relaying and Forwarding

The ubiquitous presence of configurable lighting such as LED support sensors to transmit their data through optical wireless channels, known as VLC enabled IoT. We propose a combination of VLC and BC shown in Fig. 3.4a. In this scenario, the data originating from the sensors and sent using VLC, is converted to electrical signals at a BD, namely LiBD, and the BD then transmits the data by modulating and reflecting ambient RF signals.

The design of BD shown in Fig. 3.4b with circuit diagram (left) and manufacturing footprints (right), comprising lumped elements mounted on a thin-film inkjet-printed circuit board and an inkjet-printed coplanar waveguide antenna. A solar cell BCSC241D4 harvests modulated light from the sensors and converts the light into the voltaic signal denoted by V_{sc} . The V_{sc} feeds the positive input of a comparator (CMP) TLV7031 and an RC low-pass filter (LPF) composed by a 100 k Ω resistor ($R1$) and a 0.1 μ F capacitor ($C1$), respectively. This LPF has a cut-off frequency of 15 Hz at 3 dB, and outputs the DC component of V_{sc} , denoted by V_{LPF} for feeding the negative input of the comparator. Hence, the comparator compares the AC and DC components of V_{sc} , setting the output voltage V_{CTRL} to high(V_H), if $V_{sc} > V_{LPF}$, otherwise setting V_{CTRL} to low (V_L). The output signal V_{CTRL} is then used to control RF switch ADG919 for backscatter modulation and reflection. The RF switch is connected to the coplanar waveguide antenna, switching the termination of antenna between two loads $Z_i \in \{Z_1, Z_2\}$. Assuming that the antenna is matched to characteristic impedance Z_a , the complex reflection coefficient [104] is expressed by $\Gamma_i = (Z_i - Z_a^*) / (Z_i + Z_a)$, where $*$ denotes the complex conjugation. The corresponding modulation factor M [104] is then $M = \frac{1}{4} |\Gamma_1 - \Gamma_2|^2$. The modulator achieves the maximum of $M = 1$, when $Z_1 = \infty$ and $Z_2 = 0$ corresponding to the switch either opening or shorting the antenna termination. The signal V_{CTRL} controls the RF switch and is converted

Figure 3.5: System model of Li2BC.

from the modulated light carrying sensor data.

Here, the binary frequency shift keying (FSK) baseband signal is implemented for demonstrating sensor data transmission, such that the switching speed varies between predefined frequencies f_1 and f_2 . When the ambient RF signal with a carrier frequency of f_c arrives at the antenna, it gets mixed with the switch control signal V_{CTRL} by the switching operation. The modulated backscatter signals with frequencies $f_c \pm f_1$ and $f_c \pm f_2$ will reflect and carry the sensor data. The reader detects and demodulates the backscattered signal and recovers the sensor data.

3.2.2.2 CO-END, BD with VLC Wake-up Front End and Control

We present Li2BC, a novel backscatter device that integrates VLC receiving, processing, and backscatter modulation functionalities. By utilizing a low-power microcontroller, Li2BC can receive, amplify, demodulate, and store/cache VLC signals. This caching capability enables the device to store VLC data for subsequent control of backscatter operations, enhancing its configurability and flexibility. Unlike passive devices that simply relay incoming VLC signals, Li2BC empowers more sophisticated applications by combining light-based communication with signal processing and storage functionalities, paving the way for innovative IoT solutions. Figure 3.5 shows an overview of the proposed backscatter communication system enabled by the Li2BC. The LEDs are driven by a constant current LED driver controlled by a pulse width modulation (PWM) signal. Information can be coded into the frequency of the PWM signal. As long as the frequency of the PWM is above 2 kHz [105], the information encoding does not cause visible flickering of the light. The duty cycle of the PWM signal affects the LED light intensity, and it must be held constant to avoid any flickering.

Li2BC is powered by a PV cell, which is also used to receive control data over light. As the information is encoded in a high-frequency component, it can be extracted by filtering. The filtered signal is then amplified and fed into the MCU for backscatter control. Internal capacitance and resistance of the PV cell form a circuitry resembling an LPF. This sets an upper limit for the frequency of the light intensity encoding. Depending on the cell used, this limit is in 10–20 kHz range.

The MCU communicates with BD-embedded sensors, acquiring sensing data periodically. To transmit the data with AmBC, Li2BC uses one of the MCU's timers to generate frequencies for binary FSK modulation. The MCU changes the timer parameters for every transmitted symbol. The timer can run independently, the rest of the MCU is kept in a low-power state during symbol transmission to conserve energy. The modulated signal controls an RF switch

Figure 3.6: Example of how a tag generates frequency modulation by adjusting the antenna load.

to change an antenna's reflection coefficient backscattering ambient signal. The backscattered signal can be received by commonly used RF receivers.

3.2.3 Hardware Options for Backscattering

A backscatter device reflects incoming RF signals to carry information. The tag modulates data onto these signals by changing how much of the incoming signal it reflects back. This is determined by the complex reflection coefficient Γ_i [104]. A tag changes its reflection coefficient by adjusting the load impedance connected to the antenna, as depicted in Figure 3.6. The matching between the antenna and load impedance enables the tag to fully absorb ($\Gamma = 0$), fully reflect $\Gamma = 1$ or partially reflect (Equation (3.1)) the incoming signal. Here, Z_i is the input impedance connected to the RF port going to the antenna and Z_a is the antenna impedance with * being the complex conjugate.

$$\Gamma_i = \frac{Z_i - Z_a^*}{Z_i + Z_a} \quad (3.1)$$

At its core, a backscatter device toggles or switches between loads using an RF switch. The resulting impedance mismatch attenuates the incoming signal A_{in} by a factor $|\Gamma|$ and adds a phase shift $\theta = \angle \Gamma_i$ to θ_{in} . The reflected signal has an amplitude A_{out} and phase θ_{out} .

$$A_{out} = |\Gamma_i| A_{in} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\theta_{out} = \theta_{in} + \theta \quad (3.3)$$

Different techniques, described below, exist to control the RF switch providing different benefits. Every technique has several modulation techniques that are the most suitable for it.

3.2.3.1 VCO-based

A mixed analogue-digital approach makes use of a VCO to control a RF switch [106]. A digital-to-analog converter (DAC) generates the VCO control voltage determining the backscattered frequency. This approach uses frequency based modulation techniques such as FSK and chirp spread spectrum (CSS). The resolution of the DAC is determined by the amount of symbols the hardware needs to transmit. For example, with FSK an 8-FSK scheme is able to transmit 3 bits by switching between 8 different frequencies. To achieve this the DAC needs to have an 8-bit resolution. With CSS, SF bits are transmitted per symbol resulting in 2^{SF} symbols and thus

Figure 3.7: Multi-level (8 impedances) backscattering to eliminate sidebands and harmonics.

frequencies that need to be generated. This requires at least a 2^{SF} bit DAC. A digital baseband processor¹ controls the DAC to output the appropriate chirp. The baseband processor is also responsible for constructing the data packet and translating it to symbols.

Connecting the VCO output to an RF switch with a single impedance results in a modulated square wave. This generates odd harmonics and a mirrored image causing out-of-band interference. These can be avoided by replacing the RF switch with a multi-throw variant to connect several complex impedances to the antenna. A switch mapper determines which impedance based on different phase shifted outputs of the VCO. Using multiple impedances results in intermediate backscatter levels at the antenna (Figure 3.7). Eight impedances allow to cancel the mirror image and the third and fifth harmonics. Adding additional intermediate levels allows to reduce the higher harmonics [107].

3.2.3.2 IQ-Modulator

IQ-modulators form the basis for modulation in many transmission systems. Adopting them for low-complexity backscatter tags forms a challenging task. Instead of varying the frequency of an incoming signal an IQ impedance modulator varies the phase and/or the amplitude [108], [109].

Two RF transistors generate the necessary impedances by changing their gate bias. These individually change the phase of the incoming signal. The two phase shifted signals joined in quadrature result in a new reflected wave with a phase variation range of $0-360^\circ$ within a constant voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) circle. To achieve quadrature operation, the incoming carrier signal is shifted by 45° through a delay line. The delayed signal and the carrier signal are fed to the two transistors. In the delayed line, the incident and reflected wave both experience a 45° delay causing the signal to be in quadrature with the other branch.

A baseband processor controls the transistors to vary the phase of the reflected signal. Modulation schemes occupying a limited bandwidth lower the required sample rate. This enables the use of a low-power MCU or FPGA. Overall this technique offers a flexible solution at a moderate complexity. This technique allows to suppress all harmonics [110] increasing the spectral efficiency.

¹This can either be a MCU or field-programmable gate array (FPGA).

Figure 3.8: Using direct memory access (DMA) to realize digital backscattering. CSS modulation is used as an example.

3.2.3.3 Digitally Controlled IQ-Modulator

Instead of changing the gate bias gradually to form a certain impedance, the RF switch can be switched on and off rapidly [111]. For this to function, the transistor gate control needs to be oversampled compared to the sampling clock of the receiver. The operation is analogous to dimming using PWM. The signal switches faster than perceivable by the human eye with a certain duty-cycle. After filtering this results in a DC-bias giving the lamp a proportional illumination. Here the transistor switches faster than perceivable by the receiver. Using two transistors generating out-of-phase components allows to manipulate the amplitude and phase of the backscatter signal generating points in the IQ-plane.

3.2.3.4 Digital

Eliminating the analog part in the previous approach lowers tag complexity. Additionally, analog circuits are susceptible to fluctuations in ambient temperature and supply voltage. An MCU and a single RF switch form the basis of an all digital solution [112]. The MCU emulates DDS by utilizing its DMA hardware. Before transmission, the MCU performs all necessary steps (such as scrambling, error correction coding, Gray coding, ...) to convert the data into symbols. The symbol image stored in flash memory is loaded into RAM. Once this preparation is done the DMA controller outputs the waveform by copying the RAM contents to a general-purpose input/output (GPIO). This output pin then controls the RF switch to modulate the data. Changing the DMA source address allows to transmit a different symbol (Figure 3.8).

By utilizing the DMA controller, the MCU is able to stay in a low-power mode during the largest part of a transmission. The MCU outputs a square wave containing significant harmonics. These cause interference in adjacent channels which is not the case in analog solutions [106].

3.2.3.5 Summary

Choosing the appropriate backscatter hardware depends on several factors. When minimizing complexity and power consumption is the priority, DMA-based backscatter becomes the most suitable option. However, it suffers from poor spectral efficiency due to the introduced harmonics. Analog solutions address this issue by increasing the number of backscatter impedance values, which improves spectral performance but also raises the BoM. If a lower BoM is desired, an IQ-modulator approach offers a good compromise, supporting complex modulation schemes with only moderate added complexity.

Figure 3.9: Hardware structure of the Li2BC.

Figure 3.10: Li2BC prototype with a USB serial port interface for debugging.

3.3 Wake-up Radio Design

3.3.1 Light-Controlled Wake-up Front End Designed for Li2BC

Ambient backscatter communication is a key enabler for energy-efficient IoT that employs existing RF signals for low-power communication. One open question is how to efficiently send data to the BD for waking it up and controlling its operations. Recent research reveals that the ubiquitous presence of configurable LEDs can leverage such control functionalities by involving VLC.

This section presents the wake-up front-end design of the Li2BC. By utilizing a low-power microcontroller, the VLC module of Li2BC can receive, amplify, demodulate, and store/cache VLC signals for waking up the device and further control its operation. Figure 3.9 shows the hardware structure of the Li2BC. The LEDs are driven by a constant current LED driver controlled by a PWM signal. The message used to wake up the BD can be coded into the frequency of the PWM signal. The device is powered by a PV cell, which is also used to receive wake-up (control) message over light. As the control information is encoded in a high-frequency component (e.g., > 2 kHz), it can be extracted by filtering. The filtered signal is then amplified and fed into the MCU for waking up the BD and further controlling the backscatter modulation. Internal capacitance and resistance of the PV cell form a circuitry resembling an LPF. This sets an upper limit for the frequency of the light intensity encoding. Depending on the cell used this limit is in 10–20 kHz range.

The VLC receiver is constructed as an add-on board on top of the MCU board. In the VLC receiver, the wake-up (control) signal captured by the PV cell is bandpass filtered and amplified. The amplifier utilizes Texas Instruments TLC2262 dual operational amplifier (op-amp) [113]. The op-amp is configured as a trans-impedance amplifier followed by a conventional voltage amplifier. The total amplification is 100 kVA^{-1} . The bandpass filter (BPF) turns the binary

FSK signal into on-off keying (OOK). A Schottky diode and a LPF detect the received signal envelope. Another LPF is used to measure the mean signal level.

The MCU board is based on an ultra-low-power STM32L562 [114] microcontroller from STMicroelectronics. The MCU includes comparator (COMP), timer (TIMER), and universal asynchronous receiver/transmitter (UART) that can remain operational even if the rest of the MCU is in an energy-saving sleep state. The comparator converts the mean and the envelope signals to logic-level signal. The logic-level signal is fed to the UART, which can wake the MCU for processing. The MCU board also hosts ADP5091 [115] energy harvester, which collects energy from the PV cell, and regulates all of the board voltages. The board also contains four 0.1 F supercapacitors for energy storage.

3.3.2 Wake-up Radio Processing Evaluations and Design Considerations in Cellular Internet of Things

A typical cellular IoT device will be configured to wake up periodically to listen for paging messages sent by the network. For devices that need to be reachable at short notice (often voice enabled terminals), the periodic wake-up happens every few seconds, while other devices are configured with extended sleep durations in the order of minutes.

For many IoT devices the power consumed in these discontinuous modes dominates overall battery consumption. Active periods, where user data is either received by the device or transmitted to the network, only contribute a minor portion of energy consumption over the lifetime of the product.

Keeping power consumption low during sleep intervals is relatively straight-forward and is discussed in Section 3.1.2. Here we want to focus on the energy required to wake up, synchronize, receive the paging message and go back to sleep mode.

In LTE and most NR implementations, the paging information is conveyed within the physical downlink control channel (PDCCH) channel. To receive it, a typical device will first re-synchronize to the network frequency and precise timing using either the PSS/SSS signals or CRS reference symbols embedded in the resource matrix. As a second step, the receive path channel response is estimated. The PDCCH is then received in the frequency domain (after fast Fourier transform (FFT)), the effects of the channel are compensated and the PDCCH is then decoded (e.g., using a polar decoder in NR case). The parameters encoded will reveal if the terminal is being paged.

3GPP Rel-19 introduced a new method to drastically simplify the operations required to be carried out by the terminal. A new synchronization signal called LP-SS and a new wake-up signal called LP-WUS were introduced. Crucially, both signals are encoded using OOK, although an orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) overlay sequence is also defined. The OOK modulates the magnitude of the signal only, the phase information can be disregarded. This allows the modem to process the signal in the time domain only, no frequency synchronization is necessary, and timing synchronization is much relaxed. Moreover, the signal is narrow enough in frequency so that no channel correction is needed (at least for moderately strong signal). The processing can be done largely in a fully automated, hardware-centric way without SW and complex digital signal processing (DSP) involved.

In a next deliverable, we will elaborate on the processing steps needed for conventional cellular paging reception, compare it against the NR LP-SS/LP-WUS scheme and outline further improvements possible for future protocol refinements that could be relevant to cellular A-IoT technology. We will also aim to provide a detailed budget for energy usage associated with each processing step to calculate average battery power consumption based on sleep period and other parameters.

3.4 Summary

This chapter examines END platforms for low-power IoT, BD, and wake-up radio designs, building on the proposed END concept introduced in Deliverable D2.1. It connects platform selection, sensing profiles, and computational requirements to measured energy budgets and realistic duty cycles. The chapter outlines selection criteria for microcontrollers, memory, clocks, and peripherals with deterministic wake/sleep behavior, along with firmware hooks that enable energy-aware scheduling. For backscatter systems, it details reader and tag building blocks, explains impedance modulation and radar cross-section, and relates range, throughput, and inventory latency to reader density and regulatory limits. For wake-up radios, it describes front ends, correlators, and trigger logic that minimize idle listening while bounding false-alarm probability and response time, with straightforward coupling to the main radio. Finally, the chapter provides reference interfaces, test methods, and configuration guidelines to support seamless integration with energy harvesters and multisource power management.

Chapter 4

Life Cycle Assessment

This chapter quantifies environmental impact of the core building blocks of ENDS through a component-level life cycle assessment (LCA). We define goal and scope, set boundaries from raw material extraction to end of life (EoL), and select a functional unit aligned with typical deployment of a device. The inventory covers printed circuit board (PCB), communication and processing modules, memory, energy storage, incoming energy interfaces, and casing. We outline allocation rules, data sources, and impact indicators, with global warming potential over 100 years as the primary metric. Uncertainty and sensitivity analyses identify dominant contributors, which often include storage technology and casing. Hot spots are translated into design actions, such as material substitution, modular construction, repairability, and lifetime extension.

4.1 Life Cycle Assessment of Typical Internet of Things Components

In this subsection, we delve into the environmental impact of typical components used in IoT devices, with a particular focus on elements found in ENDS. Gaining insight into the full lifecycle impact of these components is essential for developing more sustainable IoT systems. To provide a comprehensive overview, we analyze various component types, technologies, and modules such as PCBs, MCUs, wireless modules, energy sources, external memories, and RFIDs.

We quantify the environmental footprint of each component, primarily in terms of kgCO₂ equivalents. This is achieved using the Sphera LCA software, leveraging its extensive built-in and XI (Electronics 2024) extension databases. For the impact assessment, we focus specifically on the Global Warming Potential (GWP) over 100 years, using the environmental footprint (EF) 3.1 indicator, a European standard used for impact assessment categories, which is created and continuously monitored by the European Commission. This indicator encompasses both fossil and biogenic contributions and is widely recognized as a standard metric for evaluating climate-related environmental impacts.

This section is structured as follows: first, the PCBs are discussed, followed by the ICs, RF front-ends and external memories. Next, both energy storage components and energy-harvesting modules are covered. Finally, the impact of different RFIDs is examined.

Figure 4.1: PCB impact with varying number of layers

4.1.1 Impact of the Printed Circuit Board

PCBs typically only represent a small fraction of the volume of an electronic device, yet they account for an estimated 3–6% of the total weight of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) [116]. Given the electronics industry is responsible for around 4% of global greenhouse gas emissions, the contribution of PCBs to this total is far from negligible [117].

Rigid PCBs Rigid PCB are composed of a substrate, most commonly FR4 laminate, which is widely used in the electronics industry [116]. This substrate typically contains toxic brominated compounds to meet flame retardancy requirements. Depending on the PCB type, this substrate is copper-plated on one or both sides. More precisely, for multilayer PCBs, this substrate is then stacked with alternating copper and pre-preg layers, which are all compressed together. As the number of layers increases, so does the amount of copper and pre-preg material. This results in a greater environmental impact, as both the FR4 laminate and the copper layers require significant energy and solvents during production.

The impact of PCBs is assessed for different layer configurations, using a functional unit of 1 cm². The data used are based on a 2023 reference year, and modeled with a Hot Air Solder Leveling (HASL) surface finish. An attributional LCA approach is applied. As expected, the environmental impact quasi linearly with the area of the PCB and increases with the number of layers (as shown in Figure 4.1).

Flexible PCBs Flexible PCBs are manufactured using additive processes, such as screen or three-dimensional (3D) printing of conductive inks (silver or carbon-based) on flexible substrates like thin polyimide or polyester sheets [116], [118]. Although their production process is more technologically demanding compared to rigid PCBs, they are made with thinner materials and consequently require less raw materials [119]. In contrast to the subtractive etching process used for rigid PCBs, the additive printing processes used for flexible PCBs generate significantly less material waste due and reduces the use of harmful chemicals [120]. In [121], a comparative environmental analysis is conducted on various PCB configurations, differing in both substrate materials and conductive elements. Table 4.1 outlines the evaluated scenarios, covering both rigid and flexible PCB types. Figure 4.2 presents the GWP per square centimeter for each configuration, broken down by four key contributors: electricity consumption, conductive ink,

Table 4.1: Substrate and conductive material used in different scenarios.

Scenario	Substrate	Conductive Material	PCB Type
S1	FR4	Etched-Copper	Rigid PCB
S2	FR4	Ag NPs	Rigid PCB
S3	PET	Ag NPs	Flexible PCB
S4	PLA60%–GF40%	Ag NPs	Flexible PCB
S5	Paper	Ag NPs	Flexible PCB

substrate, and chemical processing. This confirms the impact improvement of additive printing processes compared to subtracting etching processes.

Flexible designs additionally often require fewer layers and can be volumetrically folded, enabling smaller device casings and potentially lower power requirements through shorter interconnections and more efficient layouts. Furthermore, in applications where the PCB is subjected to vibration or mechanical stress, flexible PCBs can even outperform rigid ones in operational durability due to their ability to absorb and withstand mechanical deformation. On the other hand, considering the shelf life of flexible PCBs, they typically last 1–2 years, while rigid PCBs can last much longer under proper storage and use. For example a rigid PCB made with FR4 can last 2-5 years and probably even longer [118], [122]. After some time, the surface finish of PCBs (e.g., HASL, ENIG, OSP) degrades and affects solderability. In the case of flexible PCBs, this degradation is accelerated because their more sensitive materials and adhesives are especially vulnerable to moisture, heat, and oxidation. On the other hand, the usable lifespan of a soldered PCB is generally in the order of 10-20 years in use [123]. However, with appropriate storage conditions and by using protective surface finishes, their shelf life can be significantly extended up to even 50-70 years [124].

Biodegradable Materials Reducing the environmental footprint of PCBs starts with reconsidering the materials used in their production. As shown in Figure 4.2, substrate selection plays a critical role: over 33% of a traditional PCB's carbon emissions are attributed to raw materials, particularly the substrate and conductive ink [121]. While using substrate materials like polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and paper already have a significant improvement, more and more attention is being given to biodegradable alternatives. The use of bio-based substrates requires less energy-intensive processing and involves fewer harmful chemicals, in contrast with traditional epoxy–fiberglass PCB substrates [116], [121]. As a result, overall environmental impacts can be reduced by as much as 60–80%, further supported by a simplified EoL process. One of the most promising candidates is polylactic acid (PLA), which has already demonstrated reliable performance in high-speed digital electronics, expecting it to be soon available in industry [116], [125].

However, while bio-based materials show great potential, most still lack the thermal and chemical stability required for harsh environments like automotive applications [116]. For now, their use will likely be limited to consumer electronics, where performance and lifetime requirements are less stringent. Although this may seem limited, it could already yield substantial environmental benefits due to the massive volume of electronics produced and discarded globally, contributing to

Figure 4.2: Impact of PCBs with different substrates and conductive materials [121]

a more sustainable and circular industry. Biodegradable PCBs typically do not last as long as their non-biodegradable counterparts. Disintegration is typically very minimal during the conditions where the PCBs are normally used. For EoL processing conditions, strongly influenced by factors such as humidity and temperature, degradation can proceed rapidly, ranging from several days for mycelium-based PCBs to a few weeks for physically large array (PLA)-based substrates [126], [127].

PCB Assembly Before a PCB can be incorporated into a final product, electronics components must be mounted onto it during assembly phase using surface mount device (SMD), through-hole technology (THT), or mixed technologies. For a representative mixed assembly process, the environmental footprint is estimated at approximately $0.5 \text{ gCO}_2\text{eq/cm}^2$ of assembled board area. This estimate is based on a representative industrial production line configuration that includes a screen printer, a THT placer, a chip shooter, a wave solder oven, and a reflow oven. This reflects a typical setup for mixed-technology PCB assembly. Variations in complexity, or the use of only THT or only SMD assembly show only negligible differences in impact.

4.1.2 Peripherals, Internal Memory and Processing

MCUs differ greatly in their internal memory, processing power, and peripheral integration. Basic MCUs, such as ARM Cortex-M0(+) cores, focus on low power consumption and have minimal features, while MCUs with RF front-ends include extra circuitry for wireless communication and processing thereof, increasing their complexity. Some MCUs incorporate specialized peripherals, such as liquid-crystal display (LCD) or USB interfaces, or feature dual-core architectures to

support more advanced applications. In this section, the impacts of different MCUs are quantified in order to determine how varying characteristics and peripherals affect their respective environmental footprint.

The environmental footprint of an IC is mainly determined by two factors: the CMOS process node technology and the physical die area of the chip. The environmental impact of the chip packaging can typically be neglected as they, e.g., are in the order of $<0.1 \text{ gCO}_2\text{eq/mm}^3$ for ball grid array (BGA) packages [128]). To accurately assess the die area, the IC's are encapsulated leaving the bare silicon die exposed. The die area can then be measured with a microscope. The process node technology (e.g., 180 nm, 90 nm, 40 nm CMOS) is identified from manufacturer data when available. Otherwise, it is estimated based on the IC's release date, comparison with similar chips of the manufacturer, and knowledge of the manufacturer's fabrication capabilities.

4.1.2.1 Modeled Components

For this study, a set of STMicroelectronics microcontrollers was modeled to capture different design characteristics relevant to environmental impact. The selection includes simple low-power Cortex-M0(+) devices (e.g., STM32L031K6U6TR, STM32U031C8U6), MCUs with additional peripherals such as an USB or LCD (e.g., STM32U073CCU6), and devices integrating RF front-ends for Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) or LoRa communication (e.g., STM32WB09KE, STM32WL55CCU6, STM32WB15CC). A high-performance variant manufactured in a smaller process node, such as the STM32WBA52CGU6, is also included. Together, these components represent the range from basic low-power designs to dual-core RF-enabled MCUs, enabling a representative comparison of their carbon footprints, showing how choices such as adding RF, integrating peripherals, or adopting smaller process nodes directly affect environmental impact. Table 4.2 gives an overview of the die areas and CMOS technology nodes used for modeling.

- STM32L031K6U6TR: Ultra-low-power ARM Cortex-M0+

This 32 MHz Cortex-M0+ microcontroller features 32 kB of Flash and 8 kB of RAM, optimized for ultra-low-power applications with multiple sleep modes.

- STM32U031C8U6: Ultra-low-power ARM Cortex-M0+

The STM32U031C8U6 microcontroller features 64 kB of Flash and 12 kB of SRAM and is an ultra-low-power 56 MHz MCU based on the Arm Cortex-M0+ 32-bit RISC core.

- STM32U073CCU6: ARM Cortex-M0+ with LCD and USB driver

Equipped with a 56 MHz Cortex-M0+ CPU, 256 kB of Flash, and 40 kB of SRAM, this MCU combines energy efficiency with integrated LCD control and USB 2.0 full-Speed support.

- STMWL55CCU6: Dual-core ARM Cortex-M4/M0+ with LoRa front-end

Featuring a dual-core 45 MHz Cortex-M4/M0+ architecture, this MCU offers 256 kB of Flash and 64 kB of RAM, and integrates a LoRa radio for low-power wireless communication in IoT applications.

- STM32WB09KE: ARM Cortex-M0+ with 2.4 GHz RF front-end (BLE)

The STM32WB09KE incorporates a 64 MHz Cortex-M0+ core with 512 kB of Flash and 64 kB of RAM. It is designed for BLE connectivity, featuring an integrated 2.4 GHz RF

Table 4.2: Impact specifications of modeled microcontroller components, including die dimensions and CMOS process technology.

Component	Width [mm]	Height [mm]	Area [mm ²]	CMOS [nm]	Source / Note
STM32L031K6U6TR	2.174	2.475	5.381	90	Based on similar ST Cortex-M0+ [129]
STM32U031C8U6	2.380	2.502	5.955	90	Given by [129]
STM32U073CCU6	2.787	2.974	8.291	90	Given by [129]
STMWL55CCU6	3.629	3.679	13.356	90	From [130]
STM32WB09KE	2.732	2.957	8.072	90	Assumed based on [129], [130]
STM32WBA52CGU6	2.723	3.053	8.313	40	From [130]
STM32WB15CC	3.388	3.336	11.302	90	From [130]

front-end supporting BLE 5.4.

- STM32WBA52CGU6: ARM Cortex-M33 with Bluetooth LE 5.4

Ultra-low-power, Cortex-M33 Trust Zone MCU 100 MHz with 1 MB of Flash memory, BLE 5.4

- STM32WB15CC: Dual-core ARM Cortex-M4/M0+ with Bluetooth LE 5.3

The STM32WB15CC is an ultra-low-power dual-core microcontroller featuring a 64 MHz ARM Cortex-M4 and a 32 MHz Cortex-M0+, with 320 kB Flash memory, featuring BLE 5.3.

4.1.2.2 Impact Comparison and Conclusion

Figure 4.3 illustrates the environmental impact of various microcontrollers, each featuring different specifications. The STM32L031K6, which is a simple low-power M0+ MCU without RF capabilities, exhibits the lowest environmental impact at 74 gCO₂eq. The impact of the STM32U031C8U6 is very similar (81.9 gCO₂eq), which is expected as they both are low-power 90 nm Cortex-M0+ MCUs. In contrast, the STM32U073CC, also a low-power Cortex-M0+ MCU, exhibits a higher impact of 114 gCO₂eq, primarily due to its integrated LCD controller and USB 2.0 support peripherals.

The RF-enabled microcontrollers exhibit notably higher impacts due to their integrated RF front-ends. A meaningful comparison can be made between the STM32L031K6U6TR and the STM32WB09KE, as both are based on the ARM Cortex-M0+ core and lack additional complex peripherals, except for the 2.4 GHz BLE RF front-end in the latter. Their impacts are 74 gCO₂eq and 111 gCO₂eq, respectively. In contrast, the STMWL55CCU6 (with 868 MHz RF frontend for LoRa communication) shows a significantly higher impact of 184 gCO₂eq, even compared to the STM32WB09KE, despite both including RF front-ends. This increase can be explained by its dual-core architecture. Furthermore, comparing the STMWL55CCU6 and STM32WB15CC, both dual-core microcontrollers with integrated RF front-ends, demonstrates that using either a BLE or LoRa front-end results in comparable environmental impacts, with emissions of ap-

Figure 4.3: Comparison of total environmental footprint of different MCUs

proximately 184 gCO₂eq and 155 gCO₂eq, respectively. Finally, the STM32WBA52CGU6 has the highest impact of 211 gCO₂eq, as it is made out of 40 nm CMOS technology to ensure its high performance capabilities [130], [131].

4.1.3 Communication

Wireless communication forms a crucial part of IoT devices, enabling communication over diverse ranges, bandwidths, and energy budgets. Requirements may vary significantly from ultra-low power and long-range communication (e.g., LoRa) to higher data throughput cellular connectivity (e.g., NB-IoT). The SiP modules typically used to enable this connectivity represent a non-negligible share of its environmental footprint due to their semiconductor content and supporting circuitry. Two representative communication technologies are analyzed in detail based on COTS components: LoRa and NB-IoT. Different antenna configurations are considered as they represent an additional contribution to the footprint of wireless communication.

LoRa Transceiver

- HopeRF RFM95W:** The LoRa transceiver includes an SX1278 LoRa transceiver, capacitors, resistors, transistors, and one LDO. The SX1278 chip is modeled using a 22 nm CMOS process with an estimated die area of 12.93 mm². The LDO is modeled using a 65 nm technology node, based on an average of the process nodes used for ALDOs and DLDOs [132].

The PCB has a surface area of 2.5 cm² and is modeled as a 4-layer FR4 board with a HASL surface finish. Assembly is assumed to take place on a medium-volume line operating at 300 units per hour. Additionally, 1 g of SnPb34Ag2 solder paste is used in the assembly

Figure 4.4: RFM95W LoRa module impact

process.

The total estimated environmental impact of the module amounts to 358 gCO₂eq, as shown in Figure 4.4.

NB-IoT Transceiver

- Nordic nRF9160:** The 16 mm x 10 mm nRF9160 SiP is a highly integrated, low-power solution for cellular IoT applications. It combines an ARM Cortex-M33 processor, Long Term Evolution for Machines (LTE-M)/NB-IoT modem, Global Positioning System (GPS), PMIC, memory, and embedded subscriber identity module (eSIM) support in a single compact package. With its built-in RF front-end and secure processing, it enables reliable, efficient, and connected edge devices. The SiP is encapsulated in a molding compound, which makes identifying individual components challenging. Nordic provides data claiming the carbon footprint of a nRF9160 is 564 gCO₂eq per unit. This value represents a cradle-to-gate for chip production, including wafer manufacturing, assembly/test, housing, leadframe, solderpaste, wirebond and transport of semi-finished goods, and components and assembly for SiP production. Other such as packaging materials, downstream transportation, use of product and EoL are not included. The processing node is not disclosed publicly, but a process node of 22 nm - 40 nm can be assumed, as these are respectively used for the nRF54 and nRF52 series [133], [134]. Since the nRF9160 was released around the same time as the nRF52 series, a process node of approximately 40 nm is a reasonable estimate. Based on previous results, the environmental footprint of a typical MCU with an integrated RF frontend, such as the STM32WBA52CGU6, is about 211 gCO₂eq. This leaves approximately 353 gCO₂eq attributable to the wireless communication and GPS module, which aligns well with the footprint of the Quectel module discussed below. To ensure proper functionality of this SiP, several additional components are required. The overall environmental impact, including these components, is illustrated in Figure 4.5.
- Quectel BC660K-GL:** This high-performance LTE Category Narrowband IoT Release 14 (Cat NB2) module, based on the Qualcomm QCX212 chipset, is specifically designed for applications in smart metering, bike sharing, smart city, agricultural monitoring and

Figure 4.5: nRF9160 SiP (including components surrounding SiP)

other related sectors. It is distinguished by its low power consumption and compact form factor [135]. The impact is estimated for both the BC660K-GL module (Figure 4.6) as the additional components required to make this NB-IoT module functional (Figure 4.7). For the former, the *electromagnetic compatibility (EMC)* casing was thermally removed, and the various components on this PCB were identified and desoldered when necessary to measure their weight (e.g., ferrite beads, oscillators, ...). Additionally, the bare die area of the QCX212 chipset was measured by mechanically removing its plastic encapsulation. For this LTE IoT modem, we deliberately chose a 45 nm process node. Furthermore, another smaller IC, probably a small MCU with some logic to encode/decode AT commands, is modeled using a 90 nm process node.

Beyond the module, several external components are needed for proper operation. These include decoupling capacitors and Zener diodes to stabilize and protect the V_{bat} supply, as well as resistors, capacitors, and diodes to interface with the *subscriber identity module (SIM)* card connector. The impact of both the SIM card connector and a physical SIM card were also taken into account. For this SIM card, the environmental impact was estimated using data from a study conducted by Fraunhofer [136]. For all other components, the Sphera LCA tool was used to estimate the impact based on the quantity, weight, or die area of the components. The SIM card module was specifically modeled using copper, stainless steel, and thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU), based on material data commonly found in datasheets of SIM card connectors, such as the CSI-25406X-18. For a standard SIM card connector [137], these materials were carefully separated and each component was individually measured to ensure an accurate representation, yielding the following results:

- **TPU:** 0.059 g
- **Copper:** 0.110 g
- **Stainless steel:** 0.193 g

Antennas

Figure 4.6: Quetcetl BC660K-GL (only module itself)

- Dipole antenna:** a dipole antenna can be modeled using a material mix of 20% copper, 40% steel, and 40% ABS [138]. The environmental impact of such a whip-like antenna is then estimated at 3.18 gCO₂eq per gram of antenna (so respectively 0.785 gCO₂eq/g, 1.3 gCO₂eq/g and 1.1 gCO₂eq/g for copper, steel and PET).
- PCB antenna:** As shown in Figure 4.1, the environmental impact of a two-layer PCB is estimated at 15.9 gCO₂eq/cm². This value can be used as an approximation for the environmental impact of a PCB antenna.
- PCB-mounted THT antenna:** As an example of such an antenna, the ANT-2.4-MSA-TH1 through-hole mounted stamped and bent steel antenna can be used. This is modeled using a basic LCA model, where stainless steel is processed through stamping and bending. This specific antenna has a mass of 0.644 g, corresponding to an estimated environmental impact of 1.32 gCO₂eq. In general, the impact of such a stamped and bent stainless steel antennas can be estimated at approximately 2.05 gCO₂eq per gram of antenna.

4.1.4 External Memory

Although the use of external SRAM ICs is uncommon, their environmental impact has been calculated across various scenarios, including different operating voltages and memory sizes, to estimate how their impact might scale when integrated within an MCU. The impact of a more commonly used external electrically erasable programmable read-only memory (EEPROM) IC has also been evaluated. However, the process node values for these technologies (250 nm for SRAM and 350 nm for EEPROM) are approximate and uncertain. Additionally, the SRAM was simulated in a 250 nm node only because it is the largest available in Sphera. Therefore, a direct comparison of their environmental impacts is not meaningful.

SRAM Memory Sizes: 64 kb/256 kb/512 kb The die sizes of different volatile SRAMs, with different memory sizes, are measured and depicted below:

- 23A640T (64 kb):** die area is 1.113 mm × 2.095 mm = 2.332 mm²

Figure 4.7: Quectel BC660K-GL (including components around module)

- **23A256T** (256 kb): die area is 1.199 mm × 2.119 mm = 2.371 mm²
- **23A512T** (512 kb): die area is 2.016 mm × 2.936 mm = 5.919 mm²

The results show that the 64 kB and 256 kB SRAM chips have nearly the same die size despite their capacity difference. This suggests that for capacities close to each other, binning techniques are used to maximize yield. In contrast, the 512 kB chip does have a much larger die, indicating that higher capacities require genuinely bigger silicon areas. It is possible that also here binning happens between capacities in the same range.

SRAM Supply Voltages: 1.5–1.95 V/2.7–3.6 V 64 kB volatile SRAM with different supply voltage ranges. The die area of both the 23A64OT and 23K64OT were measured. They differ in their voltage supply range. While the 23A64OT works between 1.5–1.95 V, the 23K640 works between 2.7–3.6 V. Measuring their die area yields the following results:

- **23A640T** (1.5–1.95 V): die area is 1.113 mm × 2.095 mm = 2.33 mm²
- **23K640T** (2.7–3.6 V): die area is 2.173 mm × 1.205 mm = 2.62 mm²

Based on the large die size and 64 kB memory, the estimated areas of one SRAM cell of the 23A650T and 23K650T external memories are approximately 17.776 μm and 19.989 μm, assuming that 50% of the total die area is occupied with SRAM, and the other 50% is logic for peripherals. According to [139], these values correspond to a 350 nm or larger process node, where SRAM cells range from 9.26 μm to 50 μm. This also aligns with [140], which states that Microchip Technologies Inc. still focuses on older, mature process nodes. Since Sphera's largest available data is for 250 nm process nodes, we estimate their impact considering this technology. The impact of both memory ICs can be found in Figure 4.8.

The size difference is therefore likely due to higher voltage requirements rather than a different process node, as the die area, and consequently the SRAM cell area difference, between these two memory modules is too small [139]. Higher voltage chips need larger transistors, I/O drivers, ESD protection, and voltage safeguards, all of which increase die area.

Figure 4.8: Impact of 23A650T and 35K650T

Non-volatile versus Volatile Non-volatile EEPROM and volatile SRAM

SRAM is often manufactured using larger technology nodes, such as 350 nm [141]. However, since Sphera only supports process nodes smaller than 250 nm, this node was used for our simulations. The comparison between SRAM and EEPROM is not entirely valid, as the process nodes of these technologies are uncertain. Consequently, the technology node represented in the Sphera database is likely not the one actually used.

- **23A640T:** die area is 1.113 mm × 2.095 mm = 2.33 mm²
- **25LC640:** die area is 1.772 mm × 2.868 mm = 5.082 mm²

Impact comparison

4.1.5 Energy Storage

Energy storage components are indispensable in IoT and embedded systems, ensuring stable operation under fluctuating power demands, enabling duty-cycling strategies, and supporting wireless communication burst currents. Depending on the application, energy storage ranges from small capacitors for short-term buffering, coin cells for low-duty cycle devices, up to rechargeable lithium-based batteries for energy-demanding applications. A set of representative energy storage solutions are analysed, covering both electrostatic (aluminum capacitors or electrostatic double-layer capacitorss (EDLCs)) and electrochemical options (non-rechargeable or lithium-based rechargeable batteries).

22 mF ALU Capacitor V_{range} : 1–5 V

A 22 mF aluminum electrolytic capacitor operating within a voltage range of 1 V - 5 V was analyzed for its environmental impact using Sphera databases. The estimation is based on a reference capacitor with a mass of 15.41 g and dimensions of 18 mm in diameter and 41 mm in length. This can be scaled both by volume and weight:

- **Volume:** the total impact is 96.2 gCO₂eq

Figure 4.9: GWP of Lithium-based rechargeable battery types

- **Weight:** the total impact is 97.8 gCO₂eq

5 F EDLC V_{range} : 1–2.7 V

The environmental impact of an EDLCs can be assessed and normalized to a capacitance of 1 F. Two types of EDLCs are considered here, based on the electrode material: Graphene-based and activated carbon-based EDLCs [142], [143].

- **Graphene-based EDLCs** result in an estimated impact of 50.6 gCO₂eq/F
- **Activated carbon-based EDLCs** show an impact of 21.19 gCO₂eq/F at a rated voltage of 2.7 V (currently the most common type of EDLC).

For both types, these impacts remain relatively negligible compared to the overall environmental footprint of the full electronic system.

CR2032 V_{range} : 3–3.3 V

The environmental impact was estimated by rescaling from a 1.6 g BR1632A battery (120 mAh) to a 3.1 g CR2032 (225 mAh). So this can be scaled based on weight and capacity. This yields the following impacts (Sphera database):

- **Capacity:** the total impact is 84.3 gCO₂eq
- **Weight:** the total impact is 87.1 gCO₂eq

Lithium Rechargeable Batteries Impact varies based on battery chemistry, as shown in Figure 4.9 where the GWP for different battery types is given in gCO₂eq/Wh [144].

The lithium titanate (LTO) battery type exhibits the highest environmental impact in terms of GWP, yet it also offers the longest cycle life, which may partially offset its footprint over the battery's lifetime. In contrast, lithium ion manganese oxide (LMO) and lithium cobalt oxide (LCO) have the lowest GWP values, indicating a lower climate impact per unit of stored energy. Among the most commonly used lithium-ion battery chemistries - NCM, NCA, and more

recently LFP -, the environmental impact is relatively similar, with GWP values in a moderate range compared to the other types.

When evaluating the environmental friendliness of different battery types, the scarcity of the elements required for their production is an important criterion [145].

Battery types such as NMC, NCA, LTO, and the older NiMH and NiCd are considered less environmentally friendly, as these batteries typically contain one or two elements classified as a rising threat and three to four elements in the future risk category. In contrast, LFP batteries present a more sustainable alternative, as they contain no elements from the rising threat category and only two from the future risk category.

4.1.6 Incoming Energy

4.1.6.1 Interface with Outside World

RF WPT Interface WPT using RF signals offers a contactless way to energize autonomous or implantable systems by enabling power delivery over greater distances and through various materials compared to inductive or capacitive coupling. While ambient RF sources (e.g., Wi-Fi, cellular towers) represent an ideal, zero-added-environmental-impact power source, their extremely low power density and harvesting efficiency, which is typically under 1% due to high path losses, make them insufficient for most applications [146].

To overcome this limitation, dedicated RF power transmitters are often employed. A basic transmitter system consists of a Single-Tone, single-input single-output (SISO) antenna configuration which features components like a phase-locked loop (PLL), power amplifier (PA) and a transmit antenna. Also more advanced architectures, such as multiple-input single-output (MISO) systems, can be used to enhance power delivery through beamforming and spatial diversity. These systems typically require additional components such as phase shifters and RF combiners.

With RF energy harvesting, the power available from ambient RF waves is insufficient for most applications. A dedicated transmitter is typically necessary. As the choice of an RF transmitter architecture is highly application-specific, its environmental impact is not assessed in detail here. Instead, Section 4.1.6.2 focuses on the RF harvester, which can most of the time be used for different types of transmit systems and thus provides a generalizable basis for analysis.

Solar Panel Existing PV datasets in commonly used LCA databases are either missing or outdated. For instance, Sphera does not currently include PV datasets, while the Ecoinvent PV modules are based on production data from as early as 2005, and the IEA PVPS 2015 datasets rely on data from 2011. However, significant technological advancements and efficiency improvements have occurred over the past decade. More recent data from 2020 shows a substantial reduction in environmental impacts, with the global warming potential of monocrystalline silicon (mono-Si) PV panels ranging from 420–810 gCO₂eq/Wp [147]. This includes impacts from manufacturing, transportation to installation sites, and EoL treatment, and is calculated using the IPCC 2013 single-issue method, based on German PV production data. Unlike RF WPT, which typically requires a dedicated transmitter, solar panels can often harvest sufficient energy from ambient light.

Figure 4.10: AEM30940 EH module impact

Other Energy Sources: Piezoelectric, Ultrasonic, Thermoelectric, etc. Interfaces for other ambient energy sources vary by technology, but typically include transducers such as:

- **Piezoelectric interfaces** that facilitate coupling with mechanical vibrations or pressure fluctuations to extract energy.
- **Ultrasonic transceivers** designed to transmit and receive ultrasonic waves for wireless power transfer and EH.
- **Thermoelectric interfaces** that establish thermal contacts to exploit temperature gradients for power generation.

4.1.6.2 Hardware Needed for Harvesting

RF Harvester The AEM30940 is a commonly used energy harvester. In combination with an antenna and a buffer, this module can harvest RF from both ambient sources and dedicated RF transmitters. This section examines the environmental impact of this specific harvester. The impact of the dipole antenna has previously been discussed in Section 4.1.3, while the contribution of the buffer - comparing both a supercapacitor and an aluminum capacitor - is addressed in Section 4.1.5. The remaining impact, attributable to the AEM30940 itself, can be further divided between the harvesting IC and the necessary surrounding passive components required for proper operation [148]. For the AEM30940, a process node of 65 nm was assumed, as this technology is commonly used in energy harvesters [149], [150]. Additionally, Fujitsu reported in 2006 that their 65 nm CS200/CS200A process delivers 1.3× faster speed, 0.6× lower power and 2× higher density, compared to their 90 nm technology [151]. This makes it ideal for low-power and high-performance energy-harvesting management ICs, like the AEM30940. Recognizing that a leading company like Fujitsu has likely already (since 2006) moved to smaller technologies like their 45 nm node, we selected the 57 nm process available through Spera. An overview of these impacts is illustrated in Figure 4.10.

Solar Panel Harvester The environmental impact of the BQ25570 EH module is analyzed by breaking down its constituent components. This analysis specifically excludes the impact

Figure 4.11: BQ25570 EH module impact

associated with populating the PCB as well as the PCB material itself. Instead, it focuses solely on the manufacturing impact of the BQ25570 IC and other surrounding necessary components to ensure proper working of this IC.

4.1.7 Radio Frequency Identifications

4.1.7.1 ST25DV Series

The **ST25DV** series, including the ST25DV04KC, ST25DV16KC, and ST25DV64KC, represents an integrated solution for RFID and near-field communication (NFC) applications. Their environmental impact assessment was conducted by mechanically removing the plastic casing to expose the chip's die area.

RFID tags operating at a carrier frequency of 13.56 MHz are mostly fabricated using mature CMOS technologies, so without the need for cutting-edge process nodes. As reported in [152], several 13.56 MHz RFID chips developed around 2017 were produced using well-established nodes: four with a 180 nm process and two with a 350 nm.

Given that STMicroelectronics is capable of manufacturing at 350 nm, 180 nm, 130 nm, 90 nm, 65 nm, 45 nm, 32 nm, ... and considering that the Sphera database only provides process data for 130 nm and 250 nm technologies, the 250 nm node was selected for modeling purposes [153].

The measured die areas of the different RFID chips are as follows:

- **ST25DV04KC (4-Kbit EEPROM):** die area is 1.469 mm x 1.672 mm
- **ST25DV16KC (16-Kbit EEPROM):** die area is 1.564 mm x 1.673 mm
- **ST25DV64KC (64-Kbit EEPROM):** die area is 1.564 mm x 1.671 mm

The nearly identical die areas across the ST25DV04KC, ST25DV16KC, and ST25DV64KC suggest that they are manufactured using the same silicon die. This strongly indicates a binning strategy, where chips with partially defective memory blocks are tested and then down-binned, so

reconfigured and sold as lower-capacity EEPROMs (e.g., 4 kbit instead of 64 kbit) to maximize yield and reduce manufacturing waste [154].

4.1.7.2 NXP UCODE 9/nxpSL3S1206 Chip

The NXP UCODE 9 [155] product family of UHF RFID tags works in the 860–960 MHz band. Its die area and CMOS process are disclosed within its datasheet and are respectively: 0.16 mm² and 140 nm [155]. Using the Sphera LCA tool, the impact was simulated based on an IC with a 130 nm process node, as this is the closest available option in the Sphera database. This simulation yields an environmental footprint of 2.81 gCO₂eq.

In addition, based on a combination of internal data provided by NXP, third-party sources, and general assumptions, an estimated impact of 1.2 gCO₂eq per die was also given for this RFID. Please note that this estimation is subject to change as the manufacturing process is constantly optimized and refined throughout the product lifetime.

4.1.7.3 Monza[®] 5 UHF RFID Chip

The **Monza 5** chip became an industry standard for item-level tagging and was a key component in source tagging solutions [156]. It is an UHF RFID chip, operating in the 860–960 MHz band. The chip integrates an analog front-end, digital logic, and EEPROM memory. According to its dataset, the Monza 5, designed and fabricated by Impinj in 2016, has a die area of only 0.216 mm². However, its CMOS process node has not been publicly disclosed.

However, the Monza 5 chip has a die area comparable to that of the NXP SL3S1206, which is known to use a 140 nm process node. Both are UHF RFID chips, and based on this similarity, a process node of 130 nm is assumed for the Monza 5 as well. This assumption is further supported by the choice made for the ST25DV series, where a 250 nm node was selected for significantly larger die areas and non-UHF RFID ICs. In that context, the use of a larger and more mature process technology makes sense. This yields an environmental impact of 3.8 gCO₂eq for this Monza 5 RFID chip.

4.1.7.4 Avery Dennison RFID AD-227m5

The Monza 5 RFID chip is used within the **Avery Dennison RFID AD-227m5** inlay [157]. This integrated circuit is combined with a printed aluminum antenna and bonded to a PET substrate, forming what is known as a dry inlay. To estimate the environmental impact, the masses of the PET, aluminum, and IC components are calculated based on their respective surface areas, the known densities of the materials, and the total measured weight of the RFID inlay.

- **Area PET** is 7.745 cm², thickness PET is 0.011 cm
- **Area aluminum antenna** is 4.66 cm², thickness antenna is 0.002 cm
- **Area IC die** is 0.216 mm² [156]

So knowing that the weight distribution for aluminum and PET respectively are 2700 kg m⁻³ and 1350 kg m⁻³, the weights of these different components become:

- **Weight (total)** is 0.160 g

Figure 4.12: GWP of the Avery Dennison RFID AD-227m5

Figure 4.13: GWP comparison of different RFID chips

- **Weight aluminum** is 0.0252 g
- **Weight PET** is 0.115 g

4.1.7.5 Comparison

Above described RFIDs can be compared based on their GWP impact. As can be seen in Figure 4.13, the ST25DV series have the largest impact, due to their larger die area compared to the Monza 5 and the xpSL3S1206 UHF RFID chip.

4.1.8 Casing

This section compares the environmental impact of common materials used for electronic casings, expressed as global warming potential (GWP kgCO₂eq) per kilogram of material. By evaluating conventional plastics such as ABS and PC, biodegradable bioplastics like PLA, and

Figure 4.14: GWP comparison of casing materials

metals including steel and aluminum, Figure 4.14 highlights their relative sustainability, aiming to support more environmentally conscious material choices.

4.2 Summary

The LCA of typical IoT components shows that the overall environmental impact of IoT devices is largely determined by manufacturing hotspots. The main contributor to the total environmental impact of low-power IoT devices is in the manufacturing phase. ICs are highly optimized for energy-efficiency, but are resource- and energy-intensive to manufacture. The analysis highlights that the choice of IC type influences the impact, stressing the importance of selecting only a powerful IC when strictly needed. Additionally, wireless communication modules, especially long-range wireless communication ICs, come with a distinct impact, whereas simple RFID-based solutions can enable applications with very limited environmental impact. Similarly, minimizing the number of PCB layers and opting for renewable biodegradable PCB materials can reduce impacts.

During the use phase, energy consumption is the main driver of impacts. Both energy storage (e.g. in batteries) and incoming energy (RF WPT and solar) play a role. Depending on the amount of required energy, an optimal storage solution, either lithium-based energy storage, supercapacitors, or even non-rechargeable batteries, must balance capacity, lifetime, and environmental footprint. RF WPT must be carefully considered, since efficiencies are typically low. In this case, low-carbon renewable energy sources can lower the operational footprint of edge devices. Solar panels for example can provide an effective and sustainable alternative when conditions allow. However, the required components for such energy harvesters and their storage systems also add to the manufacturing impacts. To limit the total environmental footprint of a device, energy efficiency in operation must be complemented by careful design choices.

Overall, three strategies stand out. Extending product lifetime distributes the high production-related impacts of PCBs, ICs, and batteries over a longer period. Minimizing energy demand during operation cuts both the direct emissions and the need for large energy storage. Finally,

circular design principles, including reparability, reuse, and recovery of valuable materials, help conserve primary resources. Together, these findings show why design decisions at the component level and operational efficiency measures must be considered jointly to achieve the lowest overall life-cycle environmental impact.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

Deliverable D2.2 has advanced the work of D2.1 from taxonomy and characterization to concrete hardware solutions that enable autonomous operation of low-power Internet of Things (IoT) devices. D2.1 established classes of energy-neutral devices and clarified the relationship between capabilities and operational modes. The present document operationalizes this foundation through an integrated view of harvesting, power transfer, multisource power management, device platforms, low-power communications, wake-up strategies, and sustainability analysis. The structure spans energy harvesting (EH) and power transfer, including charge pumps for radio frequency (RF) EH, transmitter architectures, and a comparison between ambient and dedicated RF; power management circuits with emphasis on multisource strategies, energy balance monitoring, and voltage limiting; as well as device platforms, backscatter options, wake-up radio design, and a life-cycle assessment of typical components.

The deliverable is an initial report that consolidates state-of-the-art building blocks and clarifies their roles within an energy-neutral stack. In harvesting and power transfer, it documents efficient RF front ends and outlines transmitter architectures based on large-aperture arrays, lens-based beam-space processing, and reflective intelligent surfaces, which together improve end-to-end efficiency while limiting active RF chains. The analysis also explains when dedicated wireless power transfer should complement ambient sources to achieve reliable operation.

On power management, the document addresses multisource units, energy combiners, balance monitoring, and voltage limiting. It highlights complementary circuit techniques, such as dynamic voltage scaling and adaptive body biasing, to keep ultra-low-power systems within safe and efficient operating regions across variable sources.

For device-level communications, the deliverable surveys platforms and links hardware choices to energy budgets. Example platforms include DECT-2020 modules for 5G IoT scenarios. It details backscatter options and presents wake-up designs that exploit visible light control and recent cellular mechanisms with low-power synchronization and wake-up signals, which relax frequency and timing requirements and reduce processing effort.

Finally, the life cycle assessment (LCA) provides component-level impact factors and a consistent methodology for global warming potential over 100 years using the EF 3.1 indicator. This supports responsible selection of materials and modules, including energy storage and incoming energy interfaces.

The main contribution of D2.2 is a coherent map from capability needs to implementable hardware, together with selection guidance and protection strategies that are suitable for intermittent energy. This map will guide D2.3 and D2.4. The following deliverable will focus on implementation and technical details, including integration of selected harvesters and multisource power management with representative device platforms, validation of RF front ends and transmitter options in lab and field conditions, realization of wake-up paths based on visible light and cellular low-power signals, and measurement-driven energy budgets. Therefore, D2.3 will turn the consolidated options of D2.2 into concrete prototypes and reference designs that can be reused across use cases of the project. Finally, D2.4 will report a comprehensive performance evaluation of the prototypes.

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